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Deliverable D1.2:

Report on Cyber Security education programme: results after the first year of delivery of programme

Deliverable D2.2

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Abstract

Report on the annual results achieved by WP1, including reporting on the delivery of the master’s programme and self-standing learning modules.

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1 Introduction

The deliverable reports on the main activities carried out during the first year of delivering the education programmes on Cyber Security (CSES), including preparation of self-standing online modules and activities devoted to preparing the second year of education programmes. As it will be detailed in the following sections, activities have been carried out smoothly, and students' figures and feedback show that the programme has been successfully implemented. The increasing interest in Cyber Security themes and the interesting structure of the delivered program, including an Innovation and Entrepreneurship part, have met the appreciation of SPECTRO students. Moreover, the strong experience of the involved universities in delivering education programs has given students a good study environment. The transition to the second year is also proceeding smoothly, thanks to the fact that most of (almost all) the students are on track.

The document is organized into four sections (including this introduction), followed by an annex that provides all the details of the activities carried out at each university. Section 2 summarizes the activities carried out for the implementation of the first year of the CSES education programme, including project meetings, admission process, and programme development. Moreover, a summary of the lessons learned is provided, while a detailed treatment for each partner is given in the annex. Section 3 describes the implementation of the self-standing modules with a brief presentation of each course and a preliminary list of figures and feedback. Section 4 describes the two summer schools attended by AUSIR students: "AI-driven cybersecurity", held in Rennes, and "Digital Platforms for Smart Cities", held in Helsinki. Finally, the forms in the Annex, one for each university, provide detailed activities for each partner according to the scheme described in Section 2.1.

2 Report of activities

2.1 Summary report of activities

The main activities carried out in this reporting period for the Cyber Security Master program have been devoted to the implementation of the first academic year 2024-25, and to the preparation of the new academic year 2025-26. The activities related to a.y. 2024-25 have been, thus, devoted to: welcoming of the new students, implementation of the courses, Quality Assurance (including support to students and collection of students' feedback) and organization of events. As for activities related to the a.y. 2025-26, they have been mainly devoted to marketing, recruiting and dissemination events, students' enrolment, and possible redesign of some courses in the study plan.

All these activities are described in detail for each University in separate forms provided in the Appendix. Each form is mainly structured according to the following sections:

- Classes Calendar describing the implemented courses
- Enrolled Students describing the main statistics related to enrolled students
- Study Plan describing the main offered courses
- Student Progress showing the current status of the students in terms of taken ECTS
- Organized Events for the Students listing and describing the main events for the SPECTRO students, including welcoming initiatives
- Feedback from Students describing official and informal tools to collect students' feedback on the Master program and its implementation
- Marketing, Recruiting and Dissemination Activities listing and describing the main initiatives implemented to attract new students for the a.y. 2025-26 and to promote the project activities
- Lesson Learned summarizing the main lessons that have been learned during the first year and that can be useful for the improvement of the program.

In the next subsections a project-level summary of the reported activities is provided, followed by a description of the online modules and of the summer school. Then, a list of reports, one for each project partner, is given in Appendix, structured according to the above sections.

2.2 Video conferences and meetings

The CSE major was represented by the programme lead, WP1 Lead – Viktoria Villanyi – in the following Master School events and activities in 2024:

- Jan 15 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium),
- Jan 22 SPECTRO info session (online recruitment event),
- Jan 29 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium),
- Feb 13-14 MSL (Master School) & SPECTRO meeting in Brussels,
- Mar 1 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium, online module),
- Mar 2 Master School Cyber Security info session (online),
- Mar 18 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium),
- Apr 8 ELTE recruitment event,
- Apr 9 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium, online module),
- Apr 16-17 MSL & SPECTRO meeting in Valencia,
- May 6 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- May 17 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium),
- Jun 10 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Jun 13 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium, online module),
- Jun 25 MSL & SPECTRO meeting (online),
- Jul 7 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Sep 3 MSL & SPECTRO meeting (online),
- Sep 13 SPECTRO online meeting (ELTE, EITD),
- Sep 24 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Oct 3-4 EIT Digital Master School Kick-Off in Riga and MSL meeting,
- Oct 15 SPECTRO CSE online meeting (CSES consortium, online module),
- Oct 29 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Nov 22 MSL & SPECTRO meeting in Budapest,
- Nov 26 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Dec 10 SPECTRO CSE online meeting (CSES consortium, online module),

The CSE major was represented by the programme lead, WP1 Lead – Viktoria Villanyi – in the following Master School events and activities in 2025:

- January 21 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium)
- January 21 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD)
- January 24 MSL MGMT & SPECTRO Lead online meeting
- January 27 SPECTRO meeting on scholarships (with WP3)
- January 28 SPECTRO General Assembly online meeting
- February 24 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES consortium)
- February 24 MSL & SPECTRO online meeting.
- February 25 SPECTRO application info session, ELTE, Budapest
- February 27 SPECTRO General Assembly of partners in person, EURECOM, Biot, France
- March 14 The SPECTRO Interim review rehearsal online meeting
- March 26 SPECTRO interim review meeting with the European Commission Project officer in Budapest
- March 27 The SPECTRO meeting of consortium partners in Budapest
- April 8-9 MSL & SPECTRO Meeting, IMDEA Software Institute, Madrid, SPAIN
- April 29 SPECTRO Monthly WP3 online meeting - Marketing & dissemination
- April 29 SPECTRO PEC (Project Executive Committee) online meeting
- May 27 SPECTRO Monthly WP3 online meeting - Marketing & dissemination
- May 27 SPECTRO PEC (Project Executive Committee) online meeting
- June 4 CSES online consortium meeting (CSES consortium)
- June 11 SPECTRO consortium online meeting of partners pre-summer (on reporting)
- June 17 MSL MGMT & SPECTRO online meeting
- June 23 SPECTRO updates online meeting with the European Commission Project officer
- July 10-11 The WP1 Lead attended and juried the pitch competition at the end of the SPECTRO, AI-driven Cybersecurity Innovation Summer School at University of Rennes.
- August 19 SPECTRO meeting D1.2 and D2.2 review
- August 26 SPECTRO meeting D1.2 and D2.2 review

2.3 SPECTRO Cybersecurity programme (CSES) admission process

The admission and scholarship allocation process for the Cybersecurity Master Programme has been described in Deliverable D1.1, Section 3, and will not be repeated here. Readers are invited to consult that section for full details on eligibility criteria, selection procedures, and admission requirements. The Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 admission processes have been conducted according to the D1.1 guidelines

agreed by the SPECTRO consortium. Similarly, the application timeline and scholarship allocation framework are outlined in other project deliverables: for Cycle 1 (2024–2026), these details are provided in Deliverable D4.4, while for Cycle 2 (2025–2027), they are included in Deliverable D4.5.

2.3.1 Cycle 1 (2024-2026) Enrolment figures

This subsection presents a summary overview of the Cycle 1 enrolment figures for the SPECTRO Cybersecurity Master’s programme. For a detailed analysis on admissions and scholarships allocation, please refer to Deliverable 4.4.

For Cycle 1 of the SPECTRO Cybersecurity Master’s programme, a total of 69 applications were received, of which 36 came from EU candidates and 33 from non-EU applicants. Ultimately, 26 students enrolled in the programme—21 from the EU and 5 from outside the EU—falling short of the target KPI of 50 enrolments. Scholarship demand was high and 20 scholarships were awarded. Gender distribution shows a predominance of male students (21), while female enrolment stood at 5. However, all 5 enrolled female students received a scholarship. Regional analysis indicates a balanced participation from RIS and non-RIS countries, with 11 RIS and 16 non-RIS students enrolled respectively. However, all 11 RIS students enrolled to the programme received a scholarship. Nationality data reveals strong representation from Romania (10 students) and Italy (6 students). Non-EU enrolments were more dispersed, with small numbers from China, Egypt, India, and Pakistan, without significant concentration in any single country. Overall, while application numbers were encouraging, enrolments remain below target, particularly for EU students and gender diversity.

2.3.2 Cycle 2 (2025-2027): Enrolment trends

For an overview on trends related to SPECTRO's second intake, please refer to Deliverable 4.5.

2.4 Programme Development

Design the master's programme based on labour market needs has been completed (M1-M12) The conducted labour market research based on the input of the partner universities local market research and the literature research. We have updated and modified our exit-year specializations. Starting in Fall 2025, the consortium is offering seven updated specializations instead of the previous six. The following exit-year specializations will be available:

- Advanced Cryptography (ELTE)
- Quantum-resistant Cryptography (ELTE)
- System Security (UNITN)
- Circular Security (UT)
- Big Data Security (EURECOM)
- Security Technologies and Intelligence (UTU)
- Software Security (UBB)

First-Year Implementation of the SPECTRO Cybersecurity Programme

During its first year, the SPECTRO Cybersecurity Master's programme was successfully launched across seven European entry universities, delivering a 60 ECTS foundation year that combined core technical modules—such as system and network security, cryptography, software security, and ethical hacking—with an integrated Innovation & Entrepreneurship minor totaling 30 ECTS (e.g., business development labs and project courses). Students benefited from a uniform curriculum delivery across the consortium, with self-standing cybersecurity modules (10 completed) and I&E/ethics modules (5 completed) already available online, exceeding initial targets. The structure emphasized practical, hands-on experiences, including design and coding projects, lab-based exercises, and scaffolded assignments. A two-week Summer School in Rennes provided advanced technical and entrepreneurial training grounded in real-world cybersecurity challenges. The programme model—featuring academic mobility, internships, and double-degree certification—aligned closely with European labour-market needs and demonstrated strong potential to boost graduate employability in high-demand cybersecurity and innovation roles.

2.5 Lessons learnt from HEIs

A detailed summary of the lessons learned by each partner in this first academic year is reported in the partners' forms. Overall, all the partners reported a satisfaction of the students for the delivered program, which is definitely encouraging for the follow up of this innovative education program.

2.5.1 Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE)

The first implementation of the SPECTRO Cyber Security programme at ELTE (2024/2025) demonstrated strong academic quality and an enriched curriculum, notably with the launch of a new exit specialization in Quantum-Resistant Cryptography. Two new courses — Quantum Information and Post-Quantum Cryptography—were successfully introduced, while existing cybersecurity modules were revised and updated to reflect emerging industry needs. Students responded positively, with informal feedback highlighting courses such as *Introduction to Offensive Security I*, which inspired continued participation beyond mandatory requirements.

A key strength of ELTE's approach lies in student integration and personalized support. A dedicated student advisor ensured that all SPECTRO students—two from the EU, one from a non-EU country, and one parallel entry student—were well-guided and actively engaged in university life. Activities such as Welcome Week, Summer School on AI-driven Cybersecurity Innovation, and various I&E events fostered collaboration and community among students from different backgrounds.

Challenges remain in student recruitment, with local interest being lower than expected despite proactive outreach through open days, information sessions, and social media promotion. ELTE continues to strengthen ties with industry partners to provide internships and thesis opportunities, exemplified by a confirmed placement at Ericsson for 2025/2026. The Co-Location Centre and collaborations with other international MSc students have proven effective in fostering peer learning and multidisciplinary teamwork. Moving forward, ELTE aims to expand its recruitment pipeline while further enhancing the hands-on, research-driven learning experience offered through SPECTRO.

2.5.2 EURECOM

CSES is in continuation of the CSE project, in which we have built solid experience. The target audience will largely remain the same, and the lessons learned from CSE will serve as a strong foundation for CSES. We therefore see CSES as a natural and coherent transition, where the achievements of CSE can be reinforced and adapted. This continuity ensures more effective implementation and meaningful use of the insights gained.

2.5.3 Babeş-Bolyai University (UBB)

The implementation of the SPECTRO Cyber Security programme at Babeş-Bolyai University has served as a foundational opportunity to create a compelling and internationally competitive educational offer in cybersecurity. The availability of EIT Digital scholarships significantly boosted the programme's attractiveness and accessibility.

Initial challenges included navigating co-financing and administrative requirements, as this was among the first EU-co-funded projects in the Department of Computer Science. However, thanks to synergies with the AI4CI project—run under the same DIGITAL-2022-SKILLS-03 call—UBB successfully established internal procedures in HR, finance, and reporting.

The project benefitted from strong institutional backing, with leadership from high-ranking faculty and vice-rectors. Administrative support for students was also exemplary, and all students requesting housing were accommodated in modern, affordable dormitories.

Collaboration with European partners was smooth and productive. Meetings and exchanges at both national and international levels contributed to high-quality coordination. UBB's recruitment was notably successful, attracting primarily local bachelor's graduates who chose UBB as their entry university. Moving forward, UBB aims to attract more international students and encourage second-year (exit year) enrollment at UBB to strengthen its position within the SPECTRO network.

2.5.4 University of Trento(UNITN)

The promotion of the program by means of physical presentations and seminars has been done mainly locally. Next year we plan to do physical presentations also in other neighbor Universities (i.e., Bolzano, Padova, etc.), this of course besides the promotion by means of social network and other media.

Another important issue is to make the SPECTRO's students to be part of a larger community since they are too few and this could demotivate them. Since we have a parallel Cybersecurity MSc program only for local students with many courses that overlap also with SPECTRO, we created a larger community with initiatives (i.e., seminars, etc.) common to all students attending cybersecurity programs.

Last issue relates to the deadlines of the SPECTRO's calls not always aligned with the one local to the University, this can create confusion and inefficiency in the local promotion of the program. We plan to improve on this aspects in spite of the strict constraints coming from the University regulations.

2.5.5 University of Rennes (UR)

The University of Rennes gained valuable experience from the 2024 implementation of the SPECTRO Cyber Security entry programme. Student satisfaction was generally positive, yet feedback revealed areas needing improvement, especially regarding clarity of assessments and adequacy of course materials. In response, UR1 is introducing more transparent grading guidelines, enhancing teaching resources, and adopting mid-term feedback surveys to identify issues earlier. These measures will reinforce a student-centric approach and improve the learning experience.

Recruitment posed challenges in the competitive French higher education environment, where local students are less accustomed to tuition fees. While international students showed interest, attracting top local talent remains difficult. The introduction of more generous scholarships in 2025, alongside proactive follow-up with admitted candidates and greater use of alumni success stories, is expected to strengthen enrolment. UR1 also identified the importance of increasing visibility within the university and region. Efforts will include promoting student projects, organizing local demo days, and broadening dissemination activities to engage both industry and academic stakeholders.

Other lessons relate to coordination and programme delivery. Misalignment of academic calendars across partner institutions caused difficulties for some students, highlighting the need for clearer communication of timelines. Similarly, preparing students earlier for internships and thesis work has proven necessary, as delays in aligning placements may affect graduation. UR1 has already introduced internship information sessions and will continue to collaborate closely with exit universities. Administrative challenges, such as visa delays and double enrolment processes, also underline the need for earlier support and clearer guidance.

Finally, UR1 noted that building a strong community spirit greatly benefits the programme. Activities such as the EIT Kick-Off, group projects, and alumni networking enhanced student belonging and motivation. Going forward, UR1 will maintain these efforts and expand them through social events and symbolic initiatives that reinforce programme identity. Overall, the 2024 cycle provided valuable insights that are being translated into concrete improvements for 2025, ensuring stronger recruitment, higher satisfaction, and continued growth of the Cyber Security master's programme at Rennes.

2.5.6 University of Twente (UT)

The University of Twente successfully hosted five SPECTRO entry year students during the 2024-2025 academic cycle, offering a comprehensive learning environment that featured specialized coursework, structured orientation activities, and extracurricular hacking workshops. The overall delivery of the curriculum was strong, with the majority of the students progressing as expected. One

student required an oral re-examination due to an unanticipated change in instructional staff, which was resolved effectively.

A critical operational insight emerged from staffing dynamics. A full-time instructor responsible for a core module departed unexpectedly during the academic year. While the resit examination was managed competently by the remaining teaching team, a permanent replacement for this role is still being sought. In the interim, the current instructional arrangement will be maintained, with expectations for improved course continuity and quality upon successful faculty recruitment.

Internship placement, particularly for students approaching the program's exit phase, presented notable challenges. Increased background screening requirements from companies, especially impacting international students from certain national backgrounds, have complicated placement efforts. The University will continue to monitor this issue closely and develop targeted mitigation strategies.

An important innovation during the year was the integration of the Capture-the-Flag (CTF) challenges into Master's-level education through the Twente Hacking School platform. This interactive, gamified approach has been well received by students and enables scalable, automated assessment. Plans are in place to expand its application across relevant courses.

In summary, the University of Twente's experience with the SPECTRO entry year underlines the value of instructional flexibility, the need for resilient industry engagement, and the benefits of incorporating hands-on, interactive learning formats. These insights will inform the University's ongoing strategy for program enhancement and student success.

2.5.7 University of Turku (UTU)

The University of Turku's implementation of the SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year during the 2024–2025 academic cycle was characterized by a solid and well-structured academic framework. While enrollment was limited to a single student, the experience provided meaningful insights into the program's design, delivery, and potential.

The enrolled student significantly outperformed expectations, completing 86 ECTS credits and engaging in advanced elective coursework. This performance indicates that the curriculum design, workload, and scheduling are appropriate for highly motivated learners, validating the academic architecture of the entry year.

Local student recruitment emerged as a key challenge. Despite active promotion through faculty channels and academic advisors, Finnish ICT students commonly maintain employment during their studies and demonstrate hesitancy toward international mobility and associated tuition fees.

Although the SPECTRO scholarship scheme has helped alleviate some financial concerns, further strategic outreach and communication will be necessary to enhance domestic interest and participation.

Placement opportunities for internships and thesis projects—traditionally areas of difficulty—have improved in recent years and were effectively managed in this instance. Nevertheless, as the first SPECTRO cohort approaches the program's conclusion, continued support in this area will be essential to maintain positive outcomes.

In terms of curriculum integrity, the entry year remains well-aligned with the University's existing two-year Master's programme in Cyber Security, ensuring coherence across academic offerings. Initial feedback from course evaluations has been favorable, further reinforcing the program's quality.

In conclusion, despite the limitation posed by a small cohort size, the initial year has proven academically sound and operationally instructive. It has highlighted valuable opportunities to refine recruitment strategies and student support mechanisms, laying a strong foundation for future cohort development.

3. Cybersecurity Self-standing learning modules

3.1 Report on the evolution since 2024

Since 2024, the self-standing learning modules initiative has undergone significant progress, both in terms of content development and platform integration. All modules have now been fully designed, implemented, and published on the ICARUS platform.

As of August 2025, the catalogue of self-standing modules includes 15 fully-developed courses. These modules cover a wide range of cybersecurity advanced and interdisciplinary topics. Each course has been carefully designed to support self-paced, online learning and is delivered through an open enrolment model, ensuring accessibility to a global audience of learners. The modules are structured to promote hands-on engagement, with a mix of video content, quizzes and exercises, case studies, and assessment tools, all aligned with current research and industry trends.

The modules are organized in two categories: entry and advanced levels.

- Entry-level certification – Targeted at individuals without a degree or significant knowledge/experience in Cybersecurity.
- Expert-level certification – Designed for individuals with a basic background in Cyber Security and Computer Science.

By completing the self-standing online learning modules, two types of certificates can be earned:

- Cybersecurity - Basics Certificate can be obtained by a student that completes Foundations of Cybersecurity - plus two other courses from the Entry level modules and one module on I&E.
- Cybersecurity - Advanced Certificate can be obtained by a student that completes 3 courses from the Advanced modules plus one module on I&E.

3.2 Current status

The Cyber Security self-standing modules are published online on the [SPECTRO Icarus digital learning platform](#), and they are also published on the Digital Skills and Jobs Platform (DSJP).

The following table contains the name of the modules and their publication status update:

Entry Level modules (A)	Partner	Status
Foundations of Cyber Security	UTU	Online
Introduction to Malware	UTU	Online
System security 1	UR	under publication
Basic concepts of cryptography	ELTE	Online
Cyber Security for the Business User	UBB	Online
Advanced modules (B)		
Offensive Security: Applications and Systems	UT	Online
Information Hiding with Steganography	UT	Online
Ethical Hacking course on Web Application Security	UTU	Online
Mathematical Foundation of Cryptocurrency	ELTE	Online
Privacy Enhancing Technologies	ELTE	Online
Quantum Communication and Post Quantum	UBB	Online

Modules on I&E and Ethics (common with WP2)

Modules on I&E and Ethics (C)	Partner	Status
Introduction in Agile Project Management	UBB	Online
Academic Ethics and Integrity in CS	UBB	Online
Innovation Management and Digital Economy Principles	UBB	Online
Business Development 1 – What is business?	UNITN	Online

Business Development 2 – How to develop a business?	UNITN	Online
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3.3 Presentation of each course

3.3.1 Basic Concepts of Cryptography

- **Abstract**

A short introductory course covering the foundations of cryptography. Students will understand key generation, encryption/decryption, security principles, ciphers, pseudorandomness, hash functions, authenticity, and public-key systems like RSA .

- **Syllabus Highlights**

Presentation 01: Understand key generation, encryption & decryption; problems with classical ciphers; Kerckhoffs’s principle.

Presentation 02: Grasp indistinguishability and perfect security; one-time pad properties and limitations.

Presentation 03: Learn the concept of computational security.

Presentation 04: Understand pseudorandomness.

Presentation 05: Cover stream and block ciphers and modes of operation.

Presentation 06: Learn cryptographic hash functions, authenticity, integrity, and HMACs.

Presentation 07: Introduction to public-key cryptography, basics of RSA encryption and signatures.

3.3.2 Cyber Security for the Business User

- **Abstract**

This course is targeted towards business users who encounter daily cyber threats in both personal and professional contexts. It helps students understand web-based attacks, phishing, email and social scams, file policies, password management, and general workplace cybersecurity best practices.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- **Module 1:** Introduction to cybersecurity and malware evolution
- **Module 2:** Web-based attacks – phishing, malicious URLs, impersonation
- **Module 3:** Email and social media scams
- **Module 4:** File policies and secure software use

- **Module 5:** Password best practices and authentication methods
- **Module 6:** Certificates, updates, firewalls, VPNs
- **Module 7:** Preventive measures – backups and physical security

3.3.3 Foundations of Cyber Security

- **Abstract**

Welcome to the Foundations of Cyber Security course. After completing this short course, you will have the necessary understanding of the fundamentals of cyber security to proceed toward more advanced topics. You will examine system vulnerabilities, the importance of information security, cryptography, software security, firewalls, and the protection of online services.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- **Module 1:** Definitions; Principles; Threat Landscape (with quizzes)
- **Module 2:** Cryptography; Encryption in Networks; Classic & Modern Ciphers (with quizzes)
- **Module 3:** Software Security – Connectivity, Extensibility, Complexity (with quizzes)
- **Module 4:** Firewalls – Types and Web Server Weaknesses (with quizzes)

3.3.4 Introduction to Malware

- **Abstract**

After this short course, students gain a clear understanding of the evolution and prevention of malware. Topics include different types of malware and infection mechanisms used to compromise systems. The course consists of three modules, each followed by a quiz, and takes approximately 12 hours to complete. Successful quizzes (20/20 total) contribute to the SPECTRO Cyber Security Basics Certification.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- **Module 1: Malware Basics**
 - History of Malware
 - Purpose of Malware
 - Naming Conventions for Malware
 - Damage Caused by Malware
 - (Quiz)
- **Module 2: Malware Types and Trends**
 - Trojans, Rootkits, Backdoors
 - Worms, Bots, Spyware, Adware
 - Ransomware

- Macro Malware
- Mobile Malware
- (Quiz)
- **Module 3: File Viruses in the Windows PE Environment**
 - File Virus Types
 - File Virus Hiding Methods
 - (Quiz)

3.3.5 Offensive Security: Applications and Systems

- **Abstract**

After completing this short course, students will have a fundamental understanding of different aspects of offensive security, focusing on both system security and (web) application security. Inspired by CTFs (“capture the flag” competitions), the course covers areas such as OSINT, web exploitation, and reverse engineering. Participants are encouraged to apply these skills via the University of Twente's CTF platform.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- Module 1: Introduction to OSINT
- Module 2: OSINT Examples
- Module 3: OSINT Tools (*Quiz*)
- Module 4: Introduction to Web Security
- Module 5: First Steps with SQL Injection (*Quiz*)
- Module 6: SQL Injection – Union Attack (*Quiz*)
- Module 7: Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) (*Quiz*)
- Module 8: Introduction to Reverse Engineering (*Quiz*)
- Module 9: A Simple Sourcecode Analysis (*Quiz*)
- Module 10: A More Advanced Sourcecode Analysis (*Quiz*)
- Module 11: Static Analysis (*Quiz*)
- Module 12: Reverse Engineering with Ghidra

3.3.6 Information Hiding with Steganography

- **Abstract**

This course explores techniques for embedding hidden data within digital media to avoid detection, providing both concealment and the methods used to reveal hidden information. It covers image formats and color models, lossy and lossless compression, spatial and transform-domain steganography (e.g. JPEG), and evaluating steganographic systems and detection

(steganalysis). Developed and delivered by the SPECTRO team to provide foundational knowledge in information hiding methodology and detection strategies.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- Introduction to Steganography: motivation, security vs. obscurity, applications
- Image file types & color models
- Compression methods: lossless (RLE, Huffman) and lossy techniques
- Spatial-domain steganography
- Transform-domain steganography (JPEG)

Evaluation criteria: steganalysis and detection techniques

3.3.7 Ethical Hacking Course on Web Application Security

- **Abstract**

This course equips students with practical skills to assess and secure web applications through ethical hacking techniques. It follows OWASP Top 10 standards, teaches lab setup for testing, and covers both client-side and server-side vulnerabilities as well as API security, reinforced by hands-on exercises and assessments.

- **Syllabus Highlights** (14 Lessons; 7 Quizzes)

- Course Introduction & Objectives
- Introduction to Ethical Hacking (Quiz)
- Web Technologies Fundamentals (Quiz)
- OWASP Web Application Top 10 (Quiz)
- Lab Setup
- Reconnaissance & Information Gathering (Quiz)
- Client-Side Attacks & Prevention (Quiz)
- Server-Side Attacks & Prevention (Quiz)
- API Security & OWASP API Top 10 (Quiz)

3.3.8 Mathematical Foundation of Cryptocurrency

- **Abstract**

This course delves into the mathematical and cryptographic foundations essential for blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies. Topics include elliptic curves, cryptographic pairings, zero-

knowledge proofs, and verifiable delay functions—providing the theoretical background necessary for understanding secure blockchain design.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- Elliptic curves
- Pairings
- Zero-knowledge proofs
- Verifiable delay functions

3.3.9 Privacy Enhancing Technologies

- **Abstract**

After completing this course, students will understand the key privacy concerns and how organizations collect and use personal data. The course introduces a range of privacy-enhancing technologies, explaining their benefits and limitations, and helps students determine when and which technologies are appropriate to use. (eit.icarus.education)

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- Introduction to Privacy: defining privacy and its associated risks
- Anonymization and De-identification Techniques: basic methods and general attack models
- Differential Privacy: understanding its principles and common implementations
- Secure Aggregation and Secure Shuffling: approaches to securely combine data from multiple clients
- Secret Sharing & Secure Multiparty Computation: techniques to privately share secrets and jointly compute functions
- Homomorphic Encryption: outsourcing computation while preserving data privacy
- Signal and Tor Protocols: implemented anonymization frameworks
- *(Final quiz)*

3.3.10 Quantum Communication and Post Quantum Cryptography

- **Abstract**

This course explores the cutting-edge intersection of quantum mechanics and cybersecurity. It delves into quantum communication technologies—such as quantum key distribution (QKD)—and their revolutionary impact on secure information exchange. Additionally, the course examines the threat posed by quantum computing to traditional cryptography and introduces post-quantum cryptographic methods designed to protect digital security in the quantum era.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- **Introduction to Quantum Mechanics and Information Theory** (4 topics with quizzes)
 - Overview of quantum states, quantum gates, circuits, and introductory quantum information concepts.
- **Quantum Key Distribution (QKD)** (4 topics with quizzes)
 - Principles of QKD, BB84 protocol, security proofs, and practical QKD implementations

3.3.11 Introduction in Agile Project Management

- **Abstract**

This course provides a comprehensive introduction to Agile Project Management, exploring its principles, methodologies, and practices essential for delivering projects efficiently in a dynamic environment.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- Module 1: Introduction to Agile Project Management – Understand the Cynefin framework and how Agile addresses complex problems.
- Module 2: Agile Manifesto – Discover the four values and twelve principles that define the Agile mindset.
- Module 3: Scrum Framework – Explore the history of Scrum, roles (Scrum Master, Product Owner, Team Members), artifacts (Backlogs, Taskboard, Definition of Done), and ceremonies (Sprint Planning, Daily Scrum, Reviews, Retrospectives).
- Module 4: Agile Estimation Techniques – Learn key concepts like User Stories, Story Points, Velocity, and other estimation strategies.
- Module 5: Extreme Programming (XP) – Dive into practices such as Pair Programming, Collective Ownership, Test-Driven Development (TDD), and Continuous Integration.
- Module 6: Lean Software Development – Understand Lean principles and the Push vs Pull approach for project efficiency.
- Module 7: Kanban – Master the Kanban system to limit work-in-progress and eliminate bottlenecks.
- Module 8: Other Agile Frameworks – Gain insight into advanced frameworks such as SAFe, Spotify Model, Crystal, and Feature-Driven Development.

3.3.12 Academic Ethics and Integrity in CS

- **Abstract**

- The course is recommended for Master students in any domain in Computer Science. The main objectives of the course are:
 - Be able to understand and apply the regulations, law and ethical practices in Computer Science
 - Detect intellectual property violations
 - Analyze risks and alternative decisions regarding ethical aspects in Computer Science
 - Be able to use ethical analysis methodologies
 - Critical abilities in identifying violation of domain's law
- **Syllabus Highlights**
 - Module 1: Introduction to Academic Ethics and Integrity on Computer Science
 - Module 2: Intellectual Property
 - Module 3: Data access, use, collection
 - Module 4: GDPR
 - Module 5: Dark Patterns
 - Module 6: Internet Regulations
 - Module 7: Privacy and Confidentiality
 - Module 8: Ethics in CS Research
 - Module 9: Risks and liabilities in Software Development
 - Module 10: Software Licenses and Open Access
 - Module 11: Ethics of AI
 - Module 12: Design for Sustainability
 - Module 13: Diversity and Inclusion

3.3.13 Innovation Management and Digital Economy Principles

- **Abstract**

The Course consists of two main sections. The first section is dedicated to current topics specific to the digital economy, and the second addresses topics in the field of innovation management. The course presents the latest trends and topics in ten interconnected modules. In the first part of the course, students will learn about the most important trends in the digital economy, about the role of data and knowledge in increasing the competitiveness of digital organizations and start-ups that aim to create platform-type applications and business models. The course presents in detail how digital organizations can use the advantages brought by artificial intelligence and some principles of the economics of artificial intelligence. Since data is one of the most important elements of a digital organization, or of a start-up that develops a digital application, the fifth course addresses concrete scenarios of business and operational models. The second part of the course addresses topics specific to innovation from both a strategic, entrepreneurial and organizational perspective.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- Module 1: Strategic trends and digital economy
- Module 2: Roles of data, information and knowledge in digital economy
- Module 3: Network and platform economics
- Module 4: Artificial intelligence in digital economy
- Module 5: Data-centric business and operational models
- Module 6: Trends and market research for innovation
- Module 7: Market adoption and technology diffusion
- Module 8: Types and patterns of innovation
- Module 9: Innovation and strategic management
- Module 10: Managing innovation within organizations

3.3.14 Business Development 1 – What is business?

- **Abstract**

This is the first module of the course Business Development. It provides a comprehensive introduction to the key functions of a business, from procurement and operations to marketing and digitalization. Students will gain a foundational understanding of how businesses operate within their environments, how they create value through supply chains, and how strategic decisions impact competitiveness. The course also explores emerging trends such as AI and Big Data, highlighting their role in modern business management.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- **The Business Environment**
 - Introduction and supply chain
 - Porter's Model
- **Procurement**
 - Purchasing portfolio models
 - Sourcing strategies
- **Operations**
 - Lean Management
 - Production Systems Classification
- **Logistics**
 - Distribution Strategy and Channels
 - Inventory and Management
- **Marketing**
 - Segmentation

- Targeting and Positioning
- **Digitalization**
 - Introduction to Digital
 - Artificial Intelligence and Big Data

3.3.15 Business Development 2 – How to develop a business?

- **Abstract**

This is the second module of the course Business Development. It explores key frameworks and strategies for building and growing a successful business. The first part of the module focuses on the business model, introducing the tools of the Business Model Canvas and Value Proposition Canvas to analyze value creation, customer engagement, and financial viability. The second part of the module provides a comprehensive overview of innovation and new product development, covering methodologies such as open innovation and design thinking to foster creativity and market-driven solutions. Through a combination of theory and practical applications, this module equips learners with the foundations to develop sustainable and competitive businesses.

- **Syllabus Highlights**

- **Business Model**
 - Business Model Canvas
 - Value Proposition Canvas
 - Business Model Canvas – Value Network
 - Business Model Canvas – Customer Interface
 - Business Model Canvas – Economic Model
 - Business Model Canvas – In Action
- **Innovation & New Product Development**
 - New Product Development I
 - New Product Development II
 - Open Innovation
 - Design Thinking I
 - Design Thinking II
 - Design Thinking III

3.4 Preliminary metrics and feedback

The table below presents, for each Cybersecurity module, the number of learners that started the course to date and how many completed it.

Course name	Number of learners that started the course	Number of learners that completed the course
Foundations of Cyber Security	28	3
Introduction to Malware	18	3
Basic concepts of cryptography	12	1
Cyber Security for the Business User	35	23
Offensive Security: Applications and Systems	6	0
Information Hiding with Steganography	6	4
Ethical Hacking course on Web Application Security	10	1
Mathematical Foundation of Cryptocurrency	6	3
Privacy Enhancing Technologies	8	1
Quantum Communication and Post Quantum Cryptography	10	3

- Total learners started: 139
- Total learners completed: 42
- Overall completion rate: 30.22%

Out of 139 learners who started the listed courses, 42 completed them, representing an overall completion rate of roughly 30%. Completion rates vary widely between courses. Cyber Security for the Business User stands out with the highest completion rate (around 68%), while several highly technical

or advanced courses—such as Basic Concepts of Cryptography and Offensive Security: Applications and Systems—saw no completions despite attracting some enrolments. This disparity may indicate differences in course difficulty, learner preparedness, or engagement. The pattern suggests that more accessible, business-oriented content retains participants more effectively, while advanced or specialised topics may require additional learner support to improve completion rates.

While the numbers are encouraging, overall participation and completion remain on the lower side, indicating room for growth. To address this, promotional efforts on social media were intensified over the summer (July and August 2025) to target learners who use quieter periods to upskill. In parallel, the Basics and Advanced certificates will be actively promoted to motivate learners who have started or completed individual modules to progress through the full set of courses and earn an official certification. Looking ahead, the planned release of additional courses is expected to further strengthen the programme’s appeal, offering a broader range of topics to attract new learners and encourage continued engagement from existing participants.

The table below presents, for each I&E module, the number of learners that started the course to date and how many completed it.

Course name	Number of learners that started the course	Number of learners that completed the course
Academic Ethics and Integrity in Computer Science	15	0
Business Development 1 – What is business?	0	0
Business Development 2 – How to develop a business?	2	0
Innovation Management & Digital Economy principles	10	0
Introduction to Agile Project management	15	0

- Total learners started: 42

- Total learners completed: 0

Innovation and Entrepreneurship (I&E) courses attracted a total of 42 learners, but none completed their modules. The very low completion rate for the courses can be explained primarily by delays in course delivery by partners, which postponed their availability on the platform. In addition, promotional campaigns during the initial rollout focused predominantly on technical robotics and cybersecurity modules, aiming first to attract learners with a scientific background. As a result, the I&E modules received comparatively less visibility in this first promotional phase and did not benefit from the same level of targeted outreach. Looking ahead, the upcoming promotion of the Basics and Advanced certificates—both of which include one mandatory I&E course—will provide a strong incentive for learners to enrol in these modules. Partners are confident that this integrated approach will significantly boost both participation and completion rates in the next period.

4. Summer Schools

In the summer of 2025, SPECTRO students participated in two dedicated Summer Schools that complemented their academic pathway with hands-on, innovation-oriented experiences. Participants could choose between the AI-Driven Cybersecurity Summer School hosted by the University of Rennes from 29 June to 12 July 2025, and the Digital Platforms for Smart Cities Summer School hosted by Aalto University in Helsinki from 11 to 22 August 2025. A total of 40 students attended the Rennes programme and 46 students joined the Helsinki programme, reflecting strong engagement across both topics. These Summer Schools offered specialised knowledge in different fields, together with opportunities for intercultural exchange, networking, and exposure to real-world challenges. This section presents a summary report for the two SPECTRO summer schools.

4.1 AI-Driven Cybersecurity, Rennes (Jun 29–Jul 12, 2025)

4.1.1 Introduction & Context

The SPECTRO–EIT Digital AI-Driven Cybersecurity Summer School took place from June 29 to July 12, 2025, at the EIT Digital Centre in Rennes, France. This fully in-person, two-week intensive is

embedded within the SPECTRO master's programme and is structured to merge rigorous technical education with entrepreneurial skills development. The event's mission: support students in converting AI-driven security concepts into viable startups, aligning with EIT Digital's model of challenge-based learning and venture creation.

4.1.2 Participants

A total of 40 students, primarily from the SPECTRO Cybersecurity MSc track along with broader EIT Digital Master School participants, took part. They were selected through a multi-stage recruitment process prioritizing diversity in academic background, gender, and geography, including participants from RIS (Regional Innovation Scheme) countries.

4.1.3 Objectives & Educational Framework

The Summer School aligns with SPECTRO's mission to integrate technical mastery and entrepreneurial readiness. Its objectives include:

1. Mastering advanced cybersecurity techniques, such as AI-powered threat detection, adversarial resilience, and quantum-safe cryptography.
2. Cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset through structured venture development: from ideation to final pitch.
3. Driving interdisciplinary teamwork, pairing students from technical and business streams on challenge-based projects.

4.1.4 Programme Structure & Activities

4.1.4.1 Weekly Agenda

Week 1 (Jun 29–Jul 5):

- Opening sessions, technical lectures, and initial venture-track introductions.
- Team formation and ideation.
- Evening social events including team-building exercises like guided tree-climbing.
- Weekend cultural excursion to Saint-Malo and Mont Saint-Michel.

Week 2 (Jul 6–Jul 12):

- Continuation of venture coaching and prototype incubation.
- An intermediate pitch session offering structured feedback.
- Final pitch day: teams present solutions to an expert jury, with leading teams granted access to a pre-incubator hosted by Rennes Innovation Hub.

4.1.4.2 *Technical Lectures & Labs*

Students immersed themselves in cutting-edge topics with hands-on components:

- AI-powered threat intelligence: detecting and analyzing advanced cyber threats.
- Adversarial resilience: securing AI models against sophisticated attacks.
- Quantum-safe cryptography: principles of future-proof encryption.
- Each lecture combined theory with lab sessions for immediate application.

4.1.4.3 *Venture Creation Track*

Following a structured three-stage methodology:

- Initial Business Concept (IBC): Teams used templates to map problem–solution scenarios, business models, and technical viability.
- Refinement Coaching: Industry coaches guided market validation, product-market fit, and business logic.
- Final Pitch: Presentations evaluated by a panel of industry experts; top teams moved into an incubator pathway.

4.1.4.4 *Keynotes from Industry*

The Summer School opened with two keynote sessions delivered by Google Cloud on AI & cybersecurity applications and by Kereval on innovation in AI testing. Subsequent keynotes included:

- INRIA on AI for network security
- University of Rennes (economics faculty) on cyber-economic risk management
- ANSSI on cybersecurity project management

These sessions provided deep corporate and research perspectives connecting AI security and innovation

4.1.4.5 *Team-Building & Cultural Activities*

Non-academic components included:

- Daily ice-breaking exercises and outdoor challenges
- Social events incorporating local cuisine
- Cultural excursion to iconic historic towns, enhancing community and cross-cultural exchange.

These helped strengthen group cohesion and peer learning.

4.1.5 **Outcomes & Metrics**

- Attendance: 40 students from diverse institutions completed the full programme.

- Prototype Delivery: Teams formed 10 ventures, with top projects accepted into pre-incubator acceleration in Rennes.
- Student Feedback: High satisfaction scores were registered, particularly about the mix of advanced content and entrepreneurship support.
- Incubator Progress: Winning teams entered local incubation pathways tied to Rennes' innovation ecosystem.

4.1.6 Reflections & Recommendations

Successes:

- Integration of AI and cybersecurity into the core curriculum.
- Effective venture creation framework.
- Strong peer and professional networking.

4.1.7 Alignment with SPECTRO Goals & KPIs

The Summer School advanced multiple strategic targets:

- Strengthened I&E module deployment (KPI6).
- Supported staff and student mobility KPIs (KPI18,19).
- Enhanced innovation pipelines through incubation prep.
- Reinforced programme visibility and recruitment momentum, even amidst earlier communications delays.

4.2 Digital Platforms for Smart Cities, Helsinki (11-22 August 2025)

4.2.1 Introduction and Context

The Digital Platforms for Smart Cities Summer School, hosted at Aalto University in Helsinki from 11–22 August 2025, was part of the EIT Digital Summer School programme. The theme responded to the growing role of digital platforms in transforming businesses, cities, and societies. Today, cities increasingly organise and expose data, which, combined with analytics and machine learning, enhances inclusiveness, engagement, and services for citizens and visitors. Mobility as a service, augmented and virtual reality applications, and intelligent platforms represent just a few examples of how smart city ecosystems are evolving. The Helsinki metropolitan area offered a highly relevant backdrop for this programme, with active engagement from local municipalities, startups, and industrial stakeholders.

4.2.2 Participants

A total of 46 SPECTRO students joined this summer school, representing both the Cybersecurity and Robotics tracks. Together with students from other EIT Digital programmes and young professionals from outside the consortium, they formed a diverse and international cohort. The group engaged in intensive teamwork and also benefited from cultural and social activities organised in Helsinki, fostering intercultural exchanges and networking opportunities.

4.2.3 Objective and Educational Framework

The objective of the programme was to provide participants with entrepreneurial and technical knowledge in digital platforms and smart city innovations. The educational framework combined lectures on platform economies, workshops on digital business models, and applied casework sourced from real-life challenges. Students learned to differentiate between traditional businesses and platforms, to understand the building blocks of multi-sided ecosystems, and to apply concepts of competitiveness and sustainability to digital platforms. Aligned with EIT Digital's Innovation and Entrepreneurship (I&E) model, the framework prioritised venture creation and problem-based learning, ensuring students acquired both conceptual and applied skills.

4.2.4 Programme Structure and Activities

Over two weeks, the programme alternated between thematic lectures, hands-on workshops, and project-based teamwork.

4.2.4.1 Weekly summative report

The two-week intensive opened on Monday 11 August with a short welcome by Lea Myyryläinen, orientation logistics, and an indoor team-based game that mixed 50+ participants into balanced teams. After a "lemonade-stand" micro-project used to practise rapid customer discovery, the cohort boarded a 16:15 bus to Seikkailupuisto Huippu adventure park for the first social evening.

Tuesday 12 August was devoted to smart-city thinking. Morning keynotes by Teemu Ropponen ("Cities, People & Data") and Indrajit Chaudhuri ("Product Management of Platforms & Products") were followed by an interview-skills mini-workshop and the first round of domain-expert interviews, setting the cadence of learning-by-doing that would last the whole fortnight.

Wednesday 13 August, starting 30 minutes late, pivoted to data-economy fundamentals. Prof. Marko Turpeinen explored sustainability lenses on data, Erik Liesola delivered the core "Platform Economy Fundamentals" lecture, and the afternoon was reserved for affinity-mapping ideation and project scoping.

Thursday 14 August focused on mobility innovation. Prof. Milos Mladenovic laid out the challenges of smart-mobility innovations, Marco Steinberg gave an architect's view on "Innovation & Design in the Age of Transformation," and the Art-of-Pitching session with Mike prepared teams for their first deliverable.

Friday 15 August mixed FinTech and urban analytics. Monika Liikamaa of Enfuce offered an insider look at payment-platform scaling, Janne Lautanala (Fintraffic) dissected large-scale data for traffic decisions, and the afternoon was dominated by the midway pitching milestone that doubled as a reality-check and coaching moment.

Weekend 16–17 August was deliberately low on lectures. Saturday was an all-day "Outdoors Day in Natural Park," giving everyone a breather and informal bonding time; Sunday was left completely free for rest or self-organised sightseeing.

Week two opened Monday 18 August with a deep dive into Aalto University's entrepreneurship ecosystem. A half-day guided tour of A Grid and the Design Factory replaced formal lectures, while Tomi Paalosmaa's talk on smart cities and Ohto Pentikäinen's demo of Doublepoint gesture-control tech kept the technical tempo high. The evening shifted to a quintessential Finnish experience: lakeside sauna and BBQ coupled with a light-hearted "fun-pitch" exercise.

Tuesday 19 August was largely reserved for project sprints—interview prep in the morning and uninterrupted prototyping in the afternoon—punctuated only by Erik Liesola's session on platform competition and competitive advantage.

Wednesday 20 August moved the cohort to the Viima building and Aalto Design Factory for a full-day hackathon-style build-and-test cycle, supported by Apurva's validation clinic and Lucy Truong's alumni fireside chat.

Thursday 21 August was the dress-rehearsal day: pitch coaching, jury Q&A, and final polish sessions ran from early morning until late afternoon, with Olli-Pekka Mutanen locking scope and deliverables.

Friday 22 August closed the programme. Morning final pitching in front of a jury led by Heli Hiden, Tarun Sharma and Natalia was immediately followed by expert-panel feedback, winner announcement, celebratory pizza lunch, and a concise wrap-up that released participants by 15:30.

4.2.4.2 Technical Lectures & Labs

Core technical content was delivered in eight compact blocks:

- Smart Cities & Urban Data

- Platform Economy & Competitive Dynamics
- Data Economy & Sustainability
- Smart-Mobility Innovation Challenges
- Product & Platform Management frameworks
- Validation & Prototyping methodologies
- Large-scale Data-Driven Decision Systems
- Gesture & Edge Interfaces

Hands-on labs took place every afternoon: lemonade-stand simulation, affinity-mapping and Crazy-8 ideation, SAM-TAM-SOM market-sizing exercise, rapid-prototyping sprints, and repeated pitch-dry-runs.

4.2.4.3 *Keynotes from Industry*

High-impact practitioner keynotes anchored each morning:

- Teemu Ropponen – City of Helsinki, “Cities, People & Data”
- Monika Liikamaa – Enfuce Oy, “Scaling a FinTech Platform”
- Janne Lautanala – Fintraffic, “Big Data for Smart Mobility”
- Ohto Pentikäinen – Doublepoint, “Gesture-Control Interfaces”
- Lucy Truong – EIT Digital Alumna, “From Summer School to Series A”

4.2.4.4 *Team-Building & Cultural Activities*

Structured bonding started on day one with an indoor game and continued outdoors at Seikkailupuisto Huippu. Saturday 16 August offered a full day “Outdoors Day in Natural Park.” The iconic lakeside sauna & BBQ on Monday 18 August blended Finnish culture with a light-hearted “fun-pitch” contest. Informal peer coaching, nightly sauna sessions, and shared meals in Aalto’s campus restaurants completed the cultural immersion, ensuring strong cross-cultural networks that outlast the programme.

4.2.5 Outcomes and Metrics

Students earned 4 ECTS credits upon completion of the summer school. Outcomes were assessed through team project work, final business model pitches, and active participation in lectures and workshops. Programme metrics included 17 hours of dedicated team project development, at least 8 thematic lectures, and engagement with 5 jury members from academia and industry. Participant feedback highlighted the strong relevance of the thematic focus, the high quality of mentoring and coaching, and the value of cultural and networking activities.

4.2.6 Reflections and Recommendations

The summer school successfully delivered on its dual promise of academic learning and entrepreneurial practice. Students particularly appreciated the chance to test their ideas against real-life cases provided by local partners, and to interact with experts from different domains. The cultural programme was equally well received, enabling networking and cohesion across a diverse group of participants. Strengthening links between summer school projects and subsequent master theses or internships was also identified as a valuable next step.

4.2.7 Alignment with SPECTRO Goals and KPIs

The summer school contributed directly to the SPECTRO objectives of fostering student mobility, interdisciplinarity, and exposure to innovation ecosystems. By travelling to Helsinki, SPECTRO students not only gained credits but also immersed themselves in a new cultural and industrial environment, building their networks and strengthening their entrepreneurial mindset. The activity supports key KPIs related to student mobility, the integration of industry challenges in the academic journey, and engagement with innovation ecosystems.

Annex A to the SPECTRO Report of activities

Deliverable D1.2:

**Report on Cyber Security education programme:
results after the first year of delivery of programme**

A1 Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE)

A1.1 Report of activities

A1.1.1 Classes calendar

At Eötvös Loránd University, the academic year consists of a fall semester and a spring semester. In the fall semester, students are required to take 28 ECTS credits of compulsory courses, while in the spring semester, they must take 32 ECTS credits of compulsory courses. In the first year of study, students are required to complete a total of 60 ECTS credits of compulsory courses at ELTE.

SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year compulsory course calendar in the academic year 2024/2025 at the Eötvös Loránd University was organized as follows:

Fall semester (9 Sep 2024 - 1 February 2025)

Compulsory Technical Courses (18 ECTS) ECTS

- Research Methodology 5
- Symmetric Key Cryptography 4
- Introduction to Offensive Security I. 4
- Privacy-enhancing Technologies 4
- Introductory Mathematics for Cybersecurity Specialisation 1

Compulsory Courses I&E (10 ECTS)

- I&E Basics 6
- Business Development Lab I. 4

Spring semester (10 February 2025 - 5 July 2025)

Compulsory Technical Courses (18 ECTS) ECTS

- Design and Analysis of Algorithms 4

- Public Key Cryptography 4
- Introduction to Data Security 4
- Advanced Software Technology 4
- Network Security 2

Compulsory I&E (14 ECTS)

- Innosocial Aspects of Entrepreneurship 6
- Thematic Innovation & Entrepreneurship project (Summer School) 4
- Business Development Lab II. 4

A1.1.2 Enrolled students

In 2024-2025 entry year cohort first (autumn) semester, three students started their studies at ELTE. Two of them are from EU countries, and one is from a non-EU country. ELTE also recruited one Hungarian parallel entry student in the fall of 2024. All of them are male students.

A1.1.3 Study plan

This is already explained in section 2.1 and in the annex provided in D1.1. Implemented as described in section 2.1, participant statistics given in section 2.6 (feedback). There were only two SPECTRO entry year EU students at ELTE. ELTE also had one non-EU and an additional EU but parallel entry student in the Cyber Security Programme.

A1.1.4 Student Progress

As of 9 July 2025, the SPECTRO cyber security entry year students at ELTE in the academic year 2024-2025 completed all compulsory technical courses, and several elective courses. These electives include technical courses relating to their studies, as well as sports courses and other courses for personal development. On average, students completed 68 credits in their first year, not including the 4 ECTS for the Thematic Innovation & Entrepreneurship project (Summer School) course, the grades for which will be entered in September.

All students are currently on track for timely graduation.

A1.1.5 Organized events for the students

The SPECTRO students at ELTE were invited to and participated in several events organized by Eötvös Loránd University and by partner institutes. These events provided excellent opportunities for the students to build their professional and personal networks, and to improve their professional skillset through acquiring new, up-to-date knowledge.

- **September 2nd – 4th** Welcome Week for Cyber Security MSc students with other international MSc students (welcome, introduction, team building, enrolment, registration, university requirements, campus tour, Budapest Node introduction, opening ceremony, information market, scavenger hunt, city tour, karaoke night)
- **October 3-4** EIT Digital Master School Kick-Off in Riga
- **May 17** Eurovision Song Contest watch party
- **June 29-July 12** Summer School on AI-driven Cybersecurity Innovation

A1.1.6 Feedback from students

We asked the following 6 questions from our students after the first semester of the programme.

Q1: Was the prior knowledge possessed sufficient for the understanding of the topics in the course?

Q02: Is the teaching load commensurate with the credits allocated?

Q03: Are the teaching materials adequate for the study of the subject?

Q04: Are the assessment procedures clearly defined?

Q05: Are you interested in the topics covered in the teaching?

Q06: Are you overall satisfied with how it was conducted?

Possible answers were:

1. Strongly positive
2. More positive than negative
3. More negative than positive
4. Strongly negative

All of our three students answered the survey. In all categories, their response was "More positive than negative".

Informally, the student coordinator has discussed the students' experiences numerous times throughout the academic year. They reported high satisfaction with the offered courses and the lecturers' expertise. They highlighted Introduction to Offensive Security I., a mandatory course they enjoyed so much that 3 out of 4 students decided to continue with the course in the spring semester (Introduction to Offensive Security II.), despite it not being mandatory for them. The SPECTRO students also actively participated in I&E events organized by Barbara Hegyi (ELTE lead of the I&E module); one student even aided her work as a teaching assistant.

A1.1.7 Workshops or Seminars offered

At ELTE, we organized a Cyber Security Seminar for SPECTRO students, which was also open to other ELTE students with an interest in the field. Our invited speakers were the Programme Coordinators from our partner institutions: Seppo Virtanen from the University of Turku (UTU) and Florian Hahn from the University of Twente (UT). They delivered an engaging guest lecture at ELTE, following the Interim Review held on March 27th in Budapest.

A1.1.8 Career Fair and job market activities

On April 10, 2025, Eötvös Loránd University organized a Career Day at the Faculty of Informatics. The 700 registered students could visit 42 company stands, find career opportunities, meet company ambassadors, receive advice on creating a successful CV and take CV photos, as well as attend mock interviews. (<https://allasborze.elte.hu/elte-karriernap-career-day/>)

A1.1.9 Marketing and recruiting activities

- **November 28, 2024:** ELTE Faculty of Informatics Open Day for high school students, link: <https://www.inf.elte.hu/nyiltnap2024ik> Despite the event targeting students yet to begin their BSc studies, a number of high schoolers are quite conscious of their preferred study plan so they had numerous questions at the EIT Digital/SPECTRO stand. We also believe it is beneficial to inform them of MSc opportunities this early on so they can plan their BSc studies accordingly. In addition, ELTE BSc students assisting with the event also approached the student coordinator to ask questions about the opportunities provided by the double degree programme. Number of participants: 900.
- **January 17, 2025:** ELTE Faculty of Informatics Open Day for high school students, link: <https://www.inf.elte.hu/nyiltnap2024ik> Similarly to the November event, numerous high schoolers and BSc students approached the student coordinator to ask questions about the opportunities provided by the double degree programmes. Number of participants: 650.

- **February 25, 2025:** Pizza session for potential applicants, Special information session for bachelor students interested in master programmes with entrepreneurship education. Number of participants: 8

- **April 2, 2025:** Facebook post for recruiting students to the SPECTRO programme. Link: <https://www.facebook.com/ELTEIKinternational/posts/pfbid0UGde8qVgaVyTjoT4p2Wn69j3wspuvA9gc4Ym71MT6ctEuvC76t1sT1vquUEeppAl>

- **May 7, 2025:** Idea Competition and EIT Digital, SPECTRO, EMAI recruitment event targeting ELTE BSc students with an interest in entrepreneurship. Number of participants: 60

- **Online Recruitment Activities for the SPECTRO Programme:**

o **ELTE Website Promotion:**

The SPECTRO Cyber Security MSc Programme is being actively promoted on ELTE's official Faculty of Informatics homepage. Link: <https://www.inf.elte.hu/content/spectro-angol-nyelvu-mesterkepzes-kettos-diplomaval.t.5756?m=801>

o **LinkedIn Outreach by Programme Lead:**

Viktória Villányi, the Programme Lead for CSES, has posted information about SPECTRO programmes and recruitment periods on her LinkedIn page to expand visibility among professionals and prospective students.

Link https://www.linkedin.com/posts/viktoria-villanyi-8566129a_spectro-university-elte-activity-7313170931500093442-5Pfd/.

A1.1.10 Dissemination activities

LinkedIn Outreach by Programme Lead:

• Viktória Villányi, the Programme Lead for CSES, has reposted information about SPECTRO programmes on her LinkedIn page to expand visibility among professionals and prospective students. Link:

1. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/evolutionary-archetypes-consulting-sl_eitdigital-spectro-cybersecurity-activity-7319091030128054273-HAPT/

2. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/barbarahegyiphd_elteik-eitdigital-masterschool-activity-7321247750606475264-e1l4/

• Viktória Villányi, the Programme Lead for CSES, has reposted information about SPECTRO Cyber security self-standing modules on her LinkedIn page to expand visibility among professionals and prospective students.

Link:

1. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/icarus-ai-elearning_edtech-innovation-digitalaeducation-activity-7331076842411515904-iu0j/

- Viktória Villányi, the Programme Lead for CSES, has reposted information about SPECTRO Cyber security Summer School on her LinkedIn page to expand visibility among professionals and prospective students.

Link:

1. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/viktoria-villanyi-8566129a_aidrivitybersecurity-innovation-spectro-activity-7345773724379275265-ZMaR/
2. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/viktoria-villanyi-8566129a_aidrivitybersecurity-innovation-spectro-activity-7349701938143285249-Tp0k/

A1.1.11 Lesson learned

From the 2024/2025 academic year, ELTE started a second exit year specialization in Quantum-Secure Cryptography. ELTE implemented two new courses in this new specialization, one on quantum information and another on post-quantum cryptography. ELTE also reworked, reshaped, and updated the existing courses on Cybersecurity. We are enthusiastic to continue improving our mandatory courses and are excited to see what the next year brings.

We employ a student advisor who specifically aids EIT Digital and SPECTRO students to help them navigate local and programme requirements.

The program was promoted to potential local students several times during 2024 and 2025 by course instructors and student advisors. We recruited one parallel entry student in the fall semester of 2024.

ELTE had two EU CSES students, one non-EU student, and one parallel entry student in the 2024/2025 academic year. These students built a strong bond and participated together in different activities. We made sure they all felt included in student activities and the university environment. Our Co-Location Centre is meant to be a shared space where students from different international MSc programmes can connect and study together, work on shared projects, and learn from each other.

For the 2025/2026 year, we will have only one exit student at ELTE. He has already arranged his internship with Ericsson for the next spring semester.

We continued to build and strengthen industry connections this year to ensure we have more and more projects and opportunities to offer our students.

We are aware that our student numbers could be higher, and we are actively working on increasing our recruitment efforts. We have been organizing events to connect with local BSc students, but we have not had the desired results yet. We will continue reaching out to this target demographic.

A2 EURECOM

A2.1 Report of activities

A2.1.1 Classes calendar

At EURECOM the academic year is organized in two semesters (Fall and Spring). In 2025/2026 the calendar for Master students will follow this structure:

Welcome for International students – French Intensive classes (FLE): 1st September 2025

First semester classes: 16th September 2025 – 21st January 2026

Exam period: 22nd January 2026 – 06th February 2026

Second semester classes: 09th February 2026 – 9th June 2026

Exam period: 10th June 2026 – 26th June 2026

A2.1.2 Enrolled students

As we are exit institution, we did not have any students in the academic year 2024/2025. However, we will receive the following 9 students in 2025/2026:

- **Master EIT Digital - Cyber Security (CSES) – SPECTRO**

o 9 students: 3 females (3 EU), 6 males (4 EU, 2 non-EU)

A2.1.3 Study plan

- The courses and ECTS in 2025/2026 for the **Cyber Security (CSES)** are organized as follows:

Elective EIT Digital Security			Unit ECTS: 10.00
			Min sum of Weight:
T	Clouds	Distributed Systems and Cloud Computing	Weight: 0.50
T	ImProc	Digital Image Processing	Weight: 0.25
T	MALIS	Machine Learning and Intelligent System	Weight: 0.50
T	MobSys	Mobile communication systems	Weight: 0.50
T	QUANTIS	Quantum Information Science	Weight: 0.25
T	SysSec	System and Network Security	Weight: 0.50
Fundamentals EIT Digital Security			Unit ECTS: 5.00
			Min sum of Weight:
T	BigSec	Security and privacy for Big Data and Cloud	Weight: 0.50
T	MPC	Multiparty Computation and Blockchains	Weight: 0.50
T	MobiSec	Mobile Systems and Smartphone Security	Weight: 1.00

Innovation & entrepreneurship EIT				Unit ECTS: 6.00
				Min sum of Weight:
G	I&E	Innovation and entrepreneurship (external course)	and EIT	Weight: 1.00

Language French or another foreign language for French speakers	1
Semester project (including research methodology)	8

A2.1.4 Student Progress

As previously stated, EURECOM being an exit institution within this EIT Master Program, we did not have any student during the academic year 2024/2025. We will closely follow the 9 students expected to arrive next September for completing their year at our institution. They will need to complete their entire program of 60 ECTS (including the semester project).

A2.1.5 Organized events for the students

- **September 28, 2024:** EIT Digital Welcome meeting: Lunch organized in collaboration with Université Côte d'Azur to welcome students who joined the EIT Master program in Campus SophiaTech in 2024 together with staff involved in the project.
- **September 1, 2024:** EURECOM organizes the Welcome event for all international students which opens a 3-week program of French intensive classes. This program, which is offered for free to international students, includes guided visits to the surroundings and cultural adjustment lessons to smooth integration.
- **Mid-September 2024:** 2 to 3 days of administrative appointments are organized by the school to help students through their procedures of life in France (visa, housing, bank account opening...) and at the school (IT presentations, student life at EURECOM, etc).
- **Integration Weekend – End of September 2024:** All newcomers are invited to participate in the integration weekend, organized by the Student Association in collaboration with EURECOM. This event is not mandatory but it's encouraged as a way to get involved in Student life at the School.
- **Career Fairs:** As noted below, students are invited to join the two student fairs organized by EURECOM each year.

A2.1.6 Feedback from students

As we did not have any student participating in this program we can't provide their feedback for now. We expect to send a survey by the end of the academic year to all SPECTRO students to evaluate their satisfaction and suggest adjustments accordingly.

A2.1.7 Workshops or Seminars offered

In collaboration with UCA, we organize some EIT Digital Entrepreneurs Lunches through the Fall term to connect students with entrepreneurial interests, provide inspiration, and build networks in a casual, supportive environment.

A2.1.8 Career Fair and job market activities

In order to help the students to find a master's thesis based on an internship, EURECOMS organizes two meetings per year.

The students are invited to one of them depending on their thesis/internship period:

- In October for a departure in March,
- In March for a departure in July,

The October meeting has been organized onsite. During this meeting, there is a short presentation on EURECOM's database (called the SIFI internship database) and how to apply for thesis/internship offers on SIFI.

The SIFI thesis/internship database is regularly updated for each thesis/internship period and each time we receive a new offer from a company. There are around 150 offers on SIFI every year. In addition, EURECOM's faculty is using its network to provide internship possibilities personalized to students who have a clear project idea.

A job/internship fair has been organized with 15 to 20 tech companies in October.

A2.1.9 Marketing and recruiting activities

- EURECOM set up a web page dedicated to CSES programme within its teaching portal: <https://www.eurecom.fr/en/teaching/european-double-degree-masters/master-cyber-security>

The page contains the logo of the EIT Digital Master School Programme, a brief introduction to EIT Digital, an overview of the core courses of the programme, the list of the partner Universities (and the links to their websites). It also includes the name of the specialization offered by each partner in the second year, as well as links to the EIT Digital MS website.

- A special slide on EIT Digital master inserted in all the corporate presentations of EURECOM.

- EURECOM advertised locally and internationally the CSES master

We continued in 2024/2025 to organize various webinars:

- In France: IMT Lille, Mines Albi, ENSSAT, ENSSEIHT, Mines St Etienne, Telecom St Etienne, ECE, ECAM
- In Tunisia: Esprit and Supcom
- In EU: Polito (Italy), TU Wien (Austria), NTNU (Norway), CTU (Czech Republic), Chalmers (Sweden), ULiège (Belgium)

- We also participated in International student recruiting fairs via Campus France: Mexico, South Korea, India, China in which we used special promotion material to encourage students to join the EIT MS through our school.

Web Marketing:

EURECOM published updated presentation of the CSES programme on one portal of reference:

- On Campus France TIE, the French national directory of academic programs taught in English: <https://taughtie.campusfrance.org/tiesearch/#/program/1916>

Additionally, EURECOM also did several social media posts to promote the EIT Digital programs (LinkedIn, Instagram).

A2.1.10 Selection and admission of candidates

How the committee carried out the evaluation of applicants and who were the persons responsible for it.

We assessed all the candidates that chose EURECOM as Exit University for intake 2024.

Applications review were assigned between the program coordinator and the administrative manager. Any questionable candidates were discussed as a team.

A2.1.11 Dissemination activities

N/A

A2.1.12 Lesson learned

CSES is in continuation of the CSE project, in which we have built solid experience. The target audience will largely remain the same, and the lessons learned from CSE will serve as a strong foundation for CSES. We therefore see CSES as a natural and coherent transition, where the achievements of CSE can be reinforced and adapted. This continuity ensures more effective implementation and meaningful use of the insights gained.

A3 Babeş-Bolyai University

A3.1 Report of activities

A3.1.1 Classes calendar

At Babeş-Bolyai University, the academic year is divided into two semesters: Semester I (the fall semester) and Semester II (the spring semester). Each semester includes courses totaling 30 ECTS credits (60 ECTS credits in total for the whole academic year).

Fall semester (Semester I): 30.09.2024 - 23.02.2025

The fall semester lasts 14 weeks, interrupted by the Christmas and New Year holiday break. Out of the 14 weeks, 12 take place before the holiday, and 2 after the holiday. The 2024-2025 academic year started on September 30, 2024. Between the two semesters, there is an exam session lasting 3 weeks, followed by a 1-week vacation and a 1-week retake session.

Spring semester (Semester II): 24.02.2025 - 13.07.2025

The spring semester for first-year students also lasts 14 weeks. In the 2024-2025 academic year, it started on February 24, with an Easter break in the middle (8 weeks before the break, and 6 weeks after). At the end of the spring semester, there is an exam session lasting 3 weeks, followed by a 1-week vacation and a 1-week retake session. After that, the summer vacation begins, marking the transition between academic years.

The summer vacation period is from 14.07.2025 to 28.09.2025.

A3.1.2 Enrolled students

In the 2024-2025 academic year, Babeş-Bolyai University enrolled 8 entry-year students in the SPECTRO Cyber Security master's programme, all of whom were EU students, consisting of 6 male and 2 female students.

A3.1.3 Study plan

In the fall semester, the students had to enroll in the following courses:

- Cryptography, 7 ECTS
- Quality Aspects of Security in Software Testing, 6 ECTS
- Computer Ethics and Academic Integrity, 4 ECTS
- Digital Economy Principles - I&E Basics, 8 ECTS
- Elective course in I&E, 5 ECTS

The *Cryptography* and *Quality Aspects of Security in Software Testing* courses are technical courses in the field of cyber security. Meanwhile, *Computer Ethics and Academic Integrity* also covers research methodology topics, as required by ARACIS (the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education). The *Digital Economy Principles - I&E Basics* and the *Elective course in I&E*, as their names imply, are part of the Innovation & Entrepreneurship (I&E) minor.

For the elective course in the I&E minor during the fall semester, the following options were offered (5 ECTS each, students could choose only one):

- **Agile Project Management**
- Strategic Business Process Automation
- Business Forecasting and Predictive Modelling

The elective course effectively chosen by the students is indicated in bold.

In the spring semester, the students had to enroll in the following courses:

- Web and Internet Security, 6 ECTS
- Security Audit and Risk Management, 6 ECTS

- Innovation Management - I&E Business Development Lab, 7 ECTS
- Thematic Project with Innovation Challenge - EIT Digital Summer School, 4 ECTS
- Elective course in Cyber Security, 7 ECTS

The *Web and Internet Security* and *Security Audit and Risk Management* courses are technical courses in cyber security. The *Innovation Management - I&E Business Development Lab* and the *Thematic Project with Innovation Challenge - EIT Digital Summer School* are part of the I&E minor.

In the spring semester, the elective courses students could choose from were technical courses in cyber security. The following options were offered (7 ECTS each, students could choose only one):

- **Network Security and Administration**
- Blockchain Security
- Complex Networks in Security
- Quantum Cryptography

The elective course effectively chosen by the students is indicated in bold.

A3.1.4 Student Progress

At the time of writing this report (June 30, 2025), out of the 8 students, 7 have already obtained the maximum number of 60 ECTS credits. The 8th student has obtained 49 credits so far. The minimum required to advance to the second year is 30 credits according to Romanian legislation, and at least 48 credits according to the EIT Digital agreement. It is worth mentioning that the retake session for the spring semester has not yet taken place, it is scheduled from July 7 to July 13, 2025. Therefore, this student may ultimately obtain more ECTS credits than they currently have. All students are therefore on a good trajectory to continue with the second year of study at a partner university.

A3.1.5 Organized events for the students

During September 2024, a dedicated Teams channel was set up for students enrolled in the SPECTRO Cyber Security master's programme. This channel was used both for initial communication with these students

and for ongoing communication throughout the whole academic year, with each group being assigned a tutor - in this case, Assoc. Prof. Darius Bufnea, who also acts as the main Babeş-Bolyai University representative for the SPECTRO project. Assigning a tutor to each student group is a common practice at Babeş-Bolyai University, and in this case, it proved especially beneficial due to the particular characteristics of this master's programme, such as its international component and the need for continuous dialogue with partner universities involved in the project.

Additionally, during the Master School Kickoff event held between October 2-4, 2024, in Riga, Assoc. Prof. Darius Bufnea participated online in the meeting with representatives of the master's programmes. He delivered a presentation about, among other things, the university, the study programme, elective courses, facilities, as well as useful information about the city and accommodation to the students.

A3.1.6 Feedback from students

At the end of each semester, students enrolled in the Master's programme in Cyber Security are required to answer several questions related to the courses that make up the curriculum, regarding the quality of these courses.

These responses are anonymous, and students are actively encouraged to complete this questionnaire. It should be noted that the questionnaires are distributed to all students enrolled in these courses, not only to those following the SPECTRO Cyber Security Master's programme (this, however, increases the representativeness of the responses, as the total number of responses is higher). The results are analyzed both at the level of the Master's programme coordinator and at the level of the Department of Computer Science council and the department management. In certain specific cases, the department council may intervene by holding discussions with the course instructor or by suggesting content changes.

The questions addressed to students about each course were as follows:

Q1: Was the prior knowledge you had sufficient to understand the topics covered in the course?

Q2: Was the teaching workload appropriate relative to the credits allocated?

Q3: Were the teaching materials adequate for studying the subject?

Q4: Were the assessment procedures clearly defined?

Q5: Were you interested in the topics covered during the course?

Q6: Were you overall satisfied with how the course was conducted?

Students had to answer using a 4-star rating system, where 1 star means "Strongly negative," 2 stars "More negative than positive," 3 stars "More positive than negative," and 4 stars "Strongly positive."

For the courses listed in section 2.3 and the above questions, the following results were obtained (scale 1..4):

Course	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	# of responses
Cryptography	3.94	3.73	3.88	3.88	3.56	3.88	16
Quality Aspects of Security in Software Testing	3.81	3.81	3.75	3.63	3.56	3.63	16
Computer Ethics and Academic Integrity	3.93	3.60	3.86	3.93	3.40	3.87	16
Digital Economy Principles - I&E Basics	3.87	3.80	3.71	3.87	3.33	3.73	16
Agile Project Management	3.73	4.00	4.00	3.79	3.86	3.64	16
Web and Internet Security	3.43	3.57	3.57	3.71	3.71	3.57	14
Security Audit and Risk Management	3.43	3.50	3.38	3.36	2.93	3.36	14
Innovation Management - I&E Business Development Lab	3.71	3.92	4	3.93	4	4	14
Network Security and Administration	3.36	3.64	3.43	3.46	3.64	3.5	14

A3.1.7 Workshops or Seminars offered

Each course in the curriculum, except for the *Thematic Project with Innovation Challenge - EIT Digital Summer School*, includes, in addition to a weekly 2-hour lecture, a 1-hour weekly seminar. This seminar is usually scheduled as a 2-hour session held every two weeks (resulting in 7 seminars per course per semester). These seminars are designed to reinforce the lecture content, being predominantly interactive and conducted synchronously with the students.

We would also like to highlight three special events where industry experts were invited to speak to students enrolled in the SPECTRO Cyber Security Master's programme:

- Tudor Damian, Certified Ethical Hacker, Microsoft MVP: *Pentesting Methodologies & Tools*, April 14, 2025
- Teodor Fuică, Solutions Consultant at Palo Alto Networks: *Palo Alto Networks - Zero Trust in Cybersecurity*, April 28, 2025
- Dragoş Cojocari, Director, Product Security at Snyk: *Security is an Onion - It Has Layers and It Will Make You Cry*, May 12, 2025.

No SPECTRO funds have been used in the organization of these events.

A3.1.8 Career Fair and job market activities

Every year, Babeş-Bolyai University organizes an internship fair addressed to students enrolled in educational programmes in the field of Computer Science. This fair usually takes place at the end of February or the beginning of March; this year, it was held on March 13, 2025 (<https://www.cs.ubbcluj.ro/workshop-ul-de-practica-2025-in-atenia-studentilor-din-anul-ii-nivel-licenta-si-master/>).

There is also an internal Teams channel where all internship offers received from companies are posted for students. Following this year internship fair, approximately 25 internship offers were shared with students through this channel.

It is worth mentioning that the mandatory internship is included in the curriculum of the SPECTRO Cyber Security Master's programme in the 4th semester (the second semester of the second year). Considering that the students of this programme are currently finishing their first year, the internship fair to be held in February/March 2026 will be of greater relevance to them.

A3.1.9 Marketing and recruiting activities

For each of the three admission rounds organized by the EIT Digital Master School, a series of marketing and recruitment activities took place at UBB.

Thus, three local recruiting webinars were held specifically for UBB's undergraduate students in their 3rd year of study, particularly those enrolled in Computer Science and Mathematics programmes.

These webinars took place on the following dates:

- January 22, 2025, for the first admission round, with 41 participants (<https://www.cs.ubbcluj.ro/esti-student-in-anul-3-stiai-ca-poti-intra-la-master-inainte-sa-ti-dai-licenta-2/>)
- March 21, 2025, for the second admission round, with 26 participants (<https://www.cs.ubbcluj.ro/o-noua-sesiune-online-de-informare-despre-masteratul-de-securitate-cibernetica-desfasurat-la-facultatea-de-matematica-si-informatica-sub-egida-eit-digital/>)
- May 9, 2025, for the final admission round, with 8 participants (<https://www.cs.ubbcluj.ro/ultima-sansa-sa-intri-la-master-inainte-sa-ti-dai-licenta-2/>)

Each of these webinars was announced on the website of the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science and disseminated via mass email to 1,063 undergraduate students in their 3rd year from the fields of Computer Science, Mathematics, and Business Informatics. These events were also shared on the social media accounts of the Department of Computer Science. Moreover, external undergraduate students from other universities also participated. Additionally, the events were distributed nationally through student organizations, as well as through student leaders (student chancellors, student senators) of the faculty who had access to these networks.

We consider these recruitment events to have been a great success. Nineteen UBB bachelor's graduates were accepted into the SPECTRO Cyber Security Master's programme, where they will pursue one of the two years of study at UBB. This number does not include UBB bachelor's graduates who were accepted into the SPECTRO Cyber Security programme at other partner universities to continue their studies (unfortunately, Babeş-Bolyai University does not have access to such data and statistics).

A3.1.10 Dissemination activities

Information about the SPECTRO project and the Cybersecurity Master's programme conducted under its umbrella was disseminated at Babeş-Bolyai University during a master's programme fair aimed at promoting the university's master's programmes, titled *UBB Master of Science Day*, which took place on March 28, 2025, and was attended, according to organizers' estimates, by between 200 and 300 participants (<https://www.cs.ubbcluj.ro/ubb-master-of-science-day-2/>).

In this context, it is worth emphasizing the synergies created between the SPECTRO project and two other EU co-funded projects: AI4CI (Artificial Intelligence for Connected Industries) - a project in which Babeş-Bolyai University is also a partner and which is carried out under the same call as SPECTRO (DIGITAL-2022-SKILLS-03) - as well as the ACHIEVE project, which, like SPECTRO, is coordinated by EIT Digital and aims to develop and run at Babeş-Bolyai University a Master's programme in Cloud and Network Infrastructure with High Performance Computing, together with several partner universities across Europe (project carried out under the DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-05 call).

A3.1.11 Lesson learned

The implementation of this project, as well as the Cyber Security master's programme developed under its umbrella, has represented an ideal opportunity to create the necessary foundation for a highly attractive educational programme for students, together with top European university partners. The scholarships offered to students through this programme by EIT Digital have undoubtedly made it more appealing, and we hope that the enrolled students and future graduates will help fill the gap in the number of cybersecurity specialists at the EU level.

Promotional poster for the Cybersecurity Master's programme presented at UBB Master of Science Day

Among the challenges identified at the institutional level were the initial implementation difficulties, as this was one of the first projects with EU co-financing and in-kind funding carried out within the Department of Computer Science of UBB. These initial challenges were overcome, in part thanks to the synergies created with the AI4CI project, which is also run by the Department of Computer Science at Babeş-Bolyai University, under the same DIGITAL-2022-SKILLS-03 call as the SPECTRO project. Thus, setting up internal processes within the Department of Computer Science and Babeş-Bolyai University in areas such as HR, finance, and co-financing was easier, as there was horizontal knowledge transfer between the management teams of the two projects.

The entire leadership of the Department of Computer Science, as well as that of the university, has been committed to this project from the very beginning. Among the members of the project implementation team were Assoc. Prof. Darius Bufnea (Cyber Security master's programme coordinator and teacher in the programme), Assoc. Prof. Adrian Sterca (Head of the Department of Computer Science and teacher in the programme), Assoc. Prof. Dan Mircea Suci (Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science

and teacher in the programme), Prof. Simona Motogna (Vice President of the UBB Senate and teacher in the programme), and Assoc. Prof. Cristian Săcărea (Vice-Rector of UBB).

Students also benefited from the support of the departmental and faculty administrative staff. Ms. Alexandrina Colț from the department office, as well as Ms. Eleonora Andreica and Ms. Liliana Pop from the dean's office, provided support to students whenever needed. Additionally, we would like to highlight that all students in the Cyber Security master's programme under the SPECTRO project who requested accommodation in the university's dormitories benefited from modern housing at affordable prices.

Collaboration with the other European partner universities and with the project coordinator was excellent and smooth. The periodic online meetings for the project work packages, as well as the in-person meetings held in Brussels, Sophia Antipolis or in Budapest, were highly beneficial and fruitful. The quality of the candidate selection process was reflected in their seriousness and commitment, with all admitted candidates currently on a good trajectory to continue their studies at the partner exit universities.

We believe that the recruitment process carried out by the Department of Computer Science at Babeș-Bolyai University was especially successful, contributing significantly to achieving the KPI regarding the number of students trained through this master's programme. At present, most students admitted to this programme are former bachelor's graduates of Babeș-Bolyai University who choose to complete the first year of the master's at UBB and the second year at a partner university abroad. In the future, we aim to attract a higher number of international students who will choose Babeș-Bolyai University for their studies, as well as to increase the number of students who wish to complete their second year (exit year) at UBB.

A4 University of Trento

A4.1 Report of activities

A4.1.1 Classes calendar

At the university of Trento, the fall semester spans across 15 weeks starting from 9th September 2024 till the week of the 16th of December. Similarly, the spring semester last 15 weeks starting from the week of the 24th of February till the week of the 2nd of June. Between the two semesters there are the Examination periods in January-February, June-July and August-September.

SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year compulsory course calendar in the academic year 2024-2025 at the University of Trento was organized with the timing below:

Fall semester, (9 Sep 2024 - 20 Dec 2024)

- Privacy and Intellectual Property Rights (6 ECTS)
- Security Testing (6 ECTS)
- Innovation and Entrepreneurship Basic (6 ECTS)

Spring semester, (24 Feb 2025 - 6 Jun 2025)

- Network Security (6 ECTS)
- Cybersecurity Risk Assessment (6 ECTS)
- Business Development Lab (9 ECTS)
- ICT Innovation (9 ECTS)

In addition to compulsory courses, students must select at least additionally 12 ECTS among the elective courses. To align the background of students coming from other universities, students must select the Introduction to Computer and Network Security course (6 ECTS) in case they did not attend any security course during their Bachelor degree.

Elective courses can be taken in both the first and the second semester based on the student's personal study plan made together with the study plan advisor. It is recommended that the study plan is balanced between semesters (that is, that the semesters will include about 30 ECTS each).

Further details:

- There are several elective courses related to Cybersecurity among these (for the academic year 2024-2025):
 - Fall Semester
 - Applied Cryptography (6 ECTS)
 - Multimedia Data Security (6 ECTS)
 - Spring Semester
 - Ethical Hacking (6 ECTS)
 - Blockchain (6 ECTS)

Other elective studies (typically in the major subject) are chosen individually for each student from the selection of annually available qualifying courses in the personal study plan so that the entry year total is 60 ECTS.

A4.1.2 Enrolled students

In the 2024-2025 academic year, the University of Trento had four enrolled EU SPECTRO cyber security entry year students (three male and one female) one of whom dropped out.

A4.1.3 Study plan

This is already explained in section 2.1. and in the annex provided in D1.1. Implemented as described in section 2.1, participant statistics given in section 2.6 (feedback). There was only three SPECTRO entry students at Trento.

A4.1.4 Organized events for the students

At the University of Trento, the orientation week for new students took place the second week of September 2024. All new students, including SPECTRO students, were invited to participate in the orientation week events and information sessions. The program-specific orientation session took

place on 16 September 2025. This was a joint event for the international Master's students starting in the local two-year cyber security program, for SPECTRO cyber security entry students, and for EIT Digital Master School Cyber Security exit students.

A4.1.5 Feedback from students

Course feedback has been collected for all the SPECTRO Cyber Security courses for the first semester. We collected 35 answers. Giving course feedback was voluntary and anonymous. The answers are included below. At the time of writing we don't have the answer for the second semester.

University of your ENTRY program

35 responses

Course name

35 responses

Q1: Was the prior knowledge possessed sufficient for the understanding of the topics in the course?

35 responses

Q02: Is the teaching load commensurate with the credits allocated?

35 responses

Q03: Are the teaching materials adequate for the study of the subject?

35 responses

Q04: Are the assessment procedures clearly defined?

35 responses

Q05: Are you interested in the topics covered in the teaching?

35 responses

Q06: Are you overall satisfied with how it was conducted
35 responses

A4.1.6 Workshops or Seminars offered

Webinar: Crypto-Chipset Security
28 April 2025

What you'll learn:

- Key security protocols
- Recent crypto system attacks
- Practical cryptography concepts
- Fundamentals of security and secure coding

Organized for all UNITN cyber security students (local programs as well as SPECTRO entry and EIT CSE exit)

A4.1.7 Career Fair and job market activities

We presented the SPECTRO program to all the students of our university and to a group of Italian local companies participating in the ICT Days event that took place from the 8th till 10th of April 2025. The ICT Days, is an initiative launched in 2009 by the [Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science](#) of the University of Trento that reached their seventeenth edition, dedicated to the Information and Communication Technology sector (ICT) and aim to boost the interaction among companies, researchers and students.

The 2025 edition is dedicated to the topic **“Humans, Robots and AI”** addressed from an ICT perspective. SPECTRO was presented the 8th of April. The full program of the initiative can be found here <https://www.ictdays.it/en/home-en/>

A4.1.8 Marketing and recruiting activities

For Trento, these should be found in the promotional activities tracker maintained by EIT digital.

A4.1.9 Lesson learned

The promotion of the program by means of physical presentations and seminars has been done mainly locally. Next year we plan to do physical presentations also in other neighbor Universities (i.e., Bolzano, Padova, etc.), this of course besides the promotion by means of social network and other media.

Another important issue is to make the SPECTRO’s students to be part of a larger community since they are too few and this could demotivate them. Since we have a parallel Cybersecurity MSc program only for local students with many courses that overlap also with SPECTRO, we created a larger community with initiatives (i.e., seminars, etc.) common to all students attending cybersecurity programs.

Last issue relates to the deadlines of the SPECTRO’s calls not always aligned with the one local to the University, this can create confusion and inefficiency in the local promotion of the program. We plan to improve on this aspects in spite of the strict constraints coming from the University regulations.

A5 University of Rennes (UR)

A5.1 Report of activities

A5.1.1 Calendar and Structure of Classes

Academic Calendar: At the University of Rennes 1 (UR1), the entry year of the Cyber Security Master's programme is organized into two semesters, autumn and spring, each carrying 30 ECTS credits. The curriculum thoughtfully balances rigorous technical cybersecurity courses with components focused on innovation and entrepreneurship (I&E). The academic year spans from September to June, in line with the French university calendar, culminating in the EIT Digital Summer School in July (further details provided in Section 6).

Curriculum Structure: The first-year curriculum at the University of Rennes 1 (UR1) for the 2024/25 academic year integrates essential cybersecurity topics with training in innovation and entrepreneurship. The followings provide a detailed overview of the course structure.

- **Semester 1 (30 ECTS):**
 - *Technical Core (20 ECTS):* **Basic Cryptography** (5 ECTS), **Low-Level Programming** (5 ECTS), **System Security** (5 ECTS), **Network Security** (5 ECTS). These compulsory courses establish foundations in cryptographic protocols, secure coding, operating system and network security concepts.
 - *I&E Module (10 ECTS):* **Innovation and Entrepreneurship** (I&E Basics, 5 ECTS) and **Business Development Laboratory 1** (5 ECTS). The I&E Basics course introduces business and innovation fundamentals, while BDL-1 is a project-based module where students form teams to develop a tech business idea.
- **Semester 2 (30 ECTS):**
 - *Technical Core (20 ECTS):* **Research Project** (5 ECTS), **Privacy** (5 ECTS), **Software Security** (5 ECTS), **Software Exploitation** (5 ECTS). In this semester, students

- undertake a research project (often in teams, simulating a mini-thesis or applied R&D project) and study advanced topics including data privacy, secure software design, and software exploitation (ethical hacking and vulnerability analysis). (*Note: “System Security” appears in the official list for Semester 2 due to a typo; the intended course is **Software Security**, distinct from the Semester 1 System Security.*)
- *I&E Module (10 ECTS): **Business Development Laboratory 2** (5 ECTS) and **Knowledge and Intangible Assets Management** (5 ECTS).* BDL-2 builds on the first-semester project (often culminating in a demo or prototype and business plan), and the KIM course teaches management of knowledge, intellectual property, and other intangible assets in tech enterprises.

The curriculum aligns closely with the shared framework of the EIT Digital Cyber Security Master’s programme. It encompasses key areas such as network architecture, cryptographic protocols, secure systems design methodologies, cyberattacks and countermeasures, IoT security, and secure software engineering. By the conclusion of the entry year, students acquire a comprehensive foundation, equipping them to address specialized security challenges in their second year. Furthermore, the integrated innovation and entrepreneurship (I&E) training fosters students’ ability to recognize business opportunities and drive innovation within the field of cybersecurity.

Workload and Pedagogy: The programme workload aligns with 60 ECTS per academic year. Typically, students enroll in four technical courses and two Innovation & Entrepreneurship (I&E) courses per semester—an arrangement generally regarded as appropriate, based on student feedback (refer to Section 7). Instructional methods integrate traditional lectures with practical laboratory sessions and project-based activities. For instance, the *Low-Level Programming* and *Software Exploitation* courses incorporate hands-on assignments involving C programming, debugging techniques, and binary exploitation. Similarly, the *System and Network Security* courses feature applied case studies and laboratory exercises focused on system and network protection. Assessment strategies encompass a variety of methods, including written examinations, project submissions, and oral presentations. Notably, the inclusion of a substantial Research Project during the second semester provides students with early exposure to research methodologies, fostering their capacity to explore complex cybersecurity challenges and produce technical documentation. Overall, the programme’s pedagogical framework prioritizes experiential and project-based learning—an essential approach in the dynamic and practice-oriented field of cybersecurity.

A5.1.2 Enrolled Students (Cohort Profile)

Cohort Size: In 2024, the University of Rennes 1 (UR1) enrolled four students in its entry-year cohort, out of a total of 28 students across the programme. This figure falls below the designated site capacity of 15 students at Rennes. The limited intake reflects a broader enrolment shortfall experienced consortium-wide in 2024, wherein only 28 of the 69 applicants who were offered admission ultimately chose to enrol. This disparity is primarily attributed to admitted candidates opting for alternative opportunities. The programme is actively implementing measures to address this gap, as detailed in Sections 9 and 11 concerning recruitment strategies and lessons learned.

Background and Diversity: The enrolled students at UR1 all held strong Bachelor's degrees in computer science or closely related fields (e.g. information engineering). They were selected through the EIT Digital Master School's centralized admissions portal, which uses a rigorous multi-criteria evaluation. Each application was reviewed by at least 3 committee members (including UR1's representative) and scored on prior academic performance, university ranking, entrepreneurial experience, and motivation. The final selection was a joint decision by the consortium's committee, ensuring a high caliber of students. Geographically, the UR1 cohort was international (including, for example, students from both EU and non-EU countries), contributing to a rich intercultural learning environment. All courses are conducted in English, and students are well-prepared in that regard.

Parallel Entry Students (PES): In the autumn 2024 intake, the University of Rennes 1 (UR1) did not receive any students through the "parallel entry" pathway—defined as students who enter the programme in Year 1 directly at their designated exit university. While a limited number of such entries were recorded across the consortium (a total of three parallel entry students), none were allocated to Rennes. Furthermore, none of the students initially enrolled at UR1 in 2024 requested a change of their assigned exit university. Across the consortium, four change-of-exit requests were submitted during the year, all of which were reviewed and approved by the programme coordinators.

Student Support: The new entrants at Rennes were immediately integrated into the local academic community and supported by the EIT Digital Student Advisor and local programme coordinator. Upon arrival, students attended orientation sessions, including an introduction to the EIT Digital Rennes Satellite (co-location centre) and meetings with faculty. Each student's study plan was reviewed to ensure prerequisites and optional choices (if any) were aligned with their background. Language support (French classes) was offered as an option, though the programme itself is in

English. All four students were assigned academic mentors (UR1 faculty members) to monitor their progress and wellbeing.

A5.1.3 Study Plan and Pedagogical Approach

Educational Philosophy: The study plan at UR1 adheres to EIT Digital’s goal of producing “*T-shaped professionals*” – i.e., students with deep technical expertise in cybersecurity (the vertical bar of the T) combined with broad skills in innovation, entrepreneurship, and teamwork (the horizontal bar). The technical curriculum covers a comprehensive range of cybersecurity topics, ensuring students gain core competencies in cryptography, system security, network defense, secure software development, and privacy technologies. According to the programme’s defined learning outcomes, by completion of the two-year Master, students will be able to “*design, code, validate and manage new secure architectures or assess and fortify existing systems to protect them from cyber threats*”. In practice, this means the first-year courses at Rennes emphasize both principles and hands-on skills so that students can confidently tackle real-world security challenges.

Skills and Topics Covered: Key knowledge areas addressed in the entry year include:

- **Secure Network Architecture and Administration** – Students learn how to design and secure networked systems, covering protocols, network attacks, and defenses. For example, in *Network Security*, they study threat models for enterprise networks and practice configuring firewalls, intrusion detection systems, etc.
- **Cryptographic Protocols and Architectures** – Through *Basic Cryptography* and advanced topics in second semester, students master symmetric and public-key cryptography, key exchange protocols, and cryptanalysis basics. These courses provide mathematical foundations and programming of cryptographic algorithms.
- **Secure Systems Design Methodology** – In *System Security* (covering OS hardening, trusted computing base, etc.) and *Privacy* (covering privacy-by-design, data protection strategies), the programme teaches methodical approaches to building security into systems architecture from the ground up.
- **Cyber Attacks and Defense (Offense/Defense)** – The *Software Exploitation* course introduces ethical hacking techniques such as binary exploitation, reverse engineering, and penetration testing. Students also see the defender’s perspective, learning to patch vulnerabilities and deploy protections. Coupled with content on Cybersecurity for Internet of

Things and emerging threats (through electives or case studies), this ensures exposure to contemporary issues in cyber defense.

- **Secure Software Engineering** – Throughout the year, an emphasis is placed on secure coding practices and software security audits. The *Software Security* course in semester 2 focuses on topics like secure design patterns, static code analysis for vulnerabilities, and web/mobile application security. Students apply this by assessing and improving the security of sample applications.

Learning in these technical areas is reinforced by extensive lab work and projects. Many courses incorporate weekly lab sessions (e.g., programming assignments in C/Python for cryptography, virtual machine exercises for system security). The *Research Project* requires students to investigate a specific cybersecurity problem (often aligned with a faculty research area or industry use-case) and produce a report/presentation, thereby training them in research methodology and scientific communication.

Innovation & Entrepreneurship Integration: A defining feature of the EIT Digital master is the parallel I&E curriculum. At UR1, students in 2024 followed the I&E Basic course and Business Development Labs as described in Section 2. The pedagogical approach to I&E is experiential: students learn fundamentals of economics, business models, and innovation management in the I&E Basics course, then immediately apply these concepts in the Business Development Lab by developing their own startup idea or product concept in the cybersecurity domain. For instance, teams might conceive a new AI-driven intrusion detection service or a privacy-enhancing mobile app, go through customer discovery, and pitch their business idea. The Summer School (between Year 1 and 2) further reinforces this – it’s a two-week intensive program where students from all sites collaborate on business challenges (see Section 6). Overall, this approach ensures students can not only build secure systems but also understand market needs and how to bring innovations to market.

UR1 leverages its experienced instructors and industry connections in teaching. The courses are taught by professors and researchers who are experts in their fields, many affiliated with renowned labs (e.g., IRISA/Inria Rennes for cybersecurity). The University has strong partnerships with regional excellence clusters (the *Pôle d'excellence cyber* in Brittany) and companies, and these experts often contribute as guest lecturers or project mentors. This enriches the pedagogical approach with real-world perspectives. For example, students might attend a seminar from an industry cybersecurity engineer or work on a project idea provided by a local startup.

Teaching Load and Support: The overall teaching load is spread reasonably throughout the year – typically 4–5 courses per semester, each with lectures and exercise sessions. Based on student feedback, the teaching load is generally seen as commensurate with the credits (most students agreed it was “more positive than negative” in balance). However, the programme is intensive, and to support student learning, UR1 provides additional resources such as tutoring sessions for difficult subjects (e.g., extra help sessions in cryptography mathematics) and open lab hours where teaching assistants are available. The tight-knit cohort at Rennes also naturally fosters peer learning and collaboration.

In summary, the pedagogical approach at UR1 marries theoretical rigor with practical training, and technical depth with innovation skills. By the end of the first year, students have not only covered the core cybersecurity domains in breadth and depth, but have also practiced teamwork, communication (through presentations and reports), and entrepreneurial thinking, which sets the stage for their specialized second year and future careers.

A5.1.4 Student Progress

Academic Performance: The academic performance of the four entry-year students at the University of Rennes 1 (UR1) in 2024 was notably strong. All students successfully passed their first-semester examinations and fulfilled the criteria for progression into the second semester. By the conclusion of the spring semester in 2025, each student had earned the full 60 ECTS credits required to complete the academic year, achieving commendable results across both technical and Innovation & Entrepreneurship (I&E) courses. There were no course repetitions or student withdrawals. Consequently, UR1 achieved a 100% retention and progression rate for the 2024/25 entry cohort—an outcome that reflects both the rigour of the admissions process, which ensured the selection of well-prepared candidates, and the academic and pastoral support provided throughout the year.

To support academic progression, the local coordinator at the University of Rennes 1 (UR1) systematically monitored each student’s performance following the first examination period and conducted individual feedback meetings. Minor academic challenges—such as one student initially encountering difficulties with the *Low-Level Programming in C* course—were promptly addressed through targeted tutoring and mentorship. As a result, the student demonstrated significant improvement by the second semester. The small cohort size enabled a high degree of individualized support, contributing to overall student success. All four UR1 students have now transitioned to

their second-year exit universities for the 2025/26 academic year, each having selected a specialization track at a partner institution in accordance with their study plan.

Progress Monitoring: Thanks to improvements in the Master School Office’s central student management system, tracking of student enrollment and progress has become more systematic and transparent across the consortium. UR1 utilized this system to verify that each student remained actively enrolled and to flag any potential withdrawal. No UR1 student withdrew in 2024; all remained active. The consortium-wide statistics indicated that, overall, 15 exit-year students were enrolled in 2024/25 and 18 students graduated in 2023/24 across the six universities. These figures show that the program is delivering graduates, though the numbers are still small. At UR1, since we do not host exit-year students, we did not have graduates in 2024; our first cohort (2018 entry) had their graduations in 2020 at their respective exit institutions. We consider the progression of our 2024 cohort to second year a success, and we will stay in touch with them during their exit year to mentor as needed (especially if any issues arise during internships or thesis work).

Completion and Graduation (Consortium Context): While UR1’s role is in the first year, we note that the overall programme had 18 students graduate in late 2024 (these were students who had started in 2022 at entry universities including Rennes, and finished their exit year in 2024). Those graduates attended the EIT Digital Graduation Ceremony in November 2024 in Budapest, which some UR1 faculty also joined to celebrate the students (including any who started at Rennes). Looking forward, the 4 students from UR1’s 2024 cohort are expected to graduate in 2026 after completing their second year. Given their performance so far and the support of the consortium, we are optimistic they will all graduate on time. One metric the consortium monitors is the fraction of students graduating within two years; to improve this, the partners have increased support particularly in the exit year (where delays can happen due to thesis or internship, see Section 11).

Continuous Improvement: Any cases of academic difficulty or delay are analyzed to improve support. For instance, across the programme it has been observed that alignment of schedules and internship timing can affect timely graduation. UR1 being an entry site doesn’t supervise internships directly, but we prepare students with a research project and we coordinate with exit sites to ensure our students transition smoothly. The programme’s new monitoring tools allow us to see if a student has not enrolled in the exit year or has paused studies, so we can follow up. In 2024, one exit student in the consortium took a leave of absence and will resume later – while not an UR1 student, this highlights the importance of tracking and advising. UR1’s coordinator participates in periodic progress meetings with the programme lead to discuss such cases and preventive measures.

Overall, student progress at UR1 in 2024 was very satisfactory. The combination of careful selection, high-quality teaching, and proactive mentoring ensured that all entry students advanced. We will carry these practices forward, and also adopt any consortium-wide improvements in progress tracking and student support.

A5.1.5 Organized Events and Seminars

Despite a modest cohort, UR1 actively integrated its students into both local and EIT Digital community events, to enhance their learning beyond the classroom:

- **EIT Digital Kick-Off 2024:** All UR1 first-year students participated in the annual Master School Kick-Off event held on October 3–4, 2024 in Riga, Latvia. This two-day event brought together new EIT Digital students from all majors. Our students joined team-building exercises, innovation challenges, and cultural activities with peers from across Europe. This was an inspiring start to their studies, where they experienced the international network of EIT Digital.
- **Local Cybersecurity Seminars:** Throughout 2024, the EIT Digital Rennes Node (and UR1's ICT department) organized frequent meetings with entrepreneurs and industry professionals in the region. Cybersecurity students were invited to these networking seminars, which typically occurred monthly. For example, in spring 2024, there were guest talks by a security architect from Orange Cyberdéfense (a company in Rennes) and a startup founder from the local cybersecurity incubator. These sessions, often informal lunch seminars or evening meetups, allowed students to hear about real-world problems and to engage in Q&A and discussions. Such events are part of the innovation ecosystem training, bridging academic learning with industry practice.
- **Cluster "Pôle d'Excellence Cyber" Events:** Rennes is at the center of Brittany's cybersecurity cluster. In November 2024, our students attended an event during European Cyber Week 2024 in Rennes (a regional conference), which included a cybersecurity job fair and tech talks. With UR1's facilitation, they got to visit company booths (e.g., Thales, Airbus Cyber) and understand the skill needs in the job market. This strengthened their exposure to potential thesis/internship hosts. UR1's partnerships with cluster members were leveraged to get free passes for our EIT students to attend these events.
- **Innovation & Entrepreneurship Events:** The EIT Digital Rennes Center also held entrepreneurship-themed events. One highlight in 2024 was a Startup Pitch Night (June 2024) where local startups (some founded by EIT Digital alumni) pitched their ventures. Our

students volunteered in the organization and were able to network with the startups. Additionally, UR1 hosted an “Innovation Days” workshop on campus in April 2024, where students from different programmes worked in teams on solving a societal challenge with digital tech. Our Cybersecurity students brought their security perspective to one of the challenges about secure smart cities. This interdisciplinary event was well received and demonstrated their ability to apply cybersecurity know-how in broader contexts.

- **Master School Meetings:** UR1 faculty and staff engaged in the consortium’s coordination meetings (mostly online). Notably, UR1 participated in SPECTRO online module meetings approximately monthly. Although these are administrative, they sometimes included students (e.g., student representatives gave feedback in a December 2024 meeting). These interactions ensured students knew their voice was heard at the program level.
- **Summer School 2025 (Preparation in 2024):** A major upcoming event is the SPECTRO Cybersecurity Summer School to be held in Rennes from June 29 to July 12, 2025. During 2024, UR1 took a leading role in planning this two-week summer program, which is focused on “AI-Driven Cybersecurity Innovation”. Our faculty designed a “Venture Creation” curriculum where students will form teams to develop an AI-cybersecurity solution addressing emerging threats. By end of 2024, we secured several high-profile speakers for this Summer School, illustrating UR1’s strong connections: for example, an opening lecture by a program manager from Kereval on AI testing, a talk by an Inria researcher on AI for network security, and a session by an economics professor on the impact of cyberattacks. These experts and others (from ANSSI, startups, etc.) will provide talks and mentorship. All our current first-year students have registered to attend this Summer School in 2025, and preparation activities (like pre-reading on AI) were provided to them in late 2024. The Summer School being hosted by University of Rennes is a testament to our commitment and capability in organizing international educational events. (Notably, the 2025 summer program is already fully booked with ~40 participants from across EIT Digital.)
- **Graduation Ceremony 2024:** Although UR1 did not host it, it’s worth noting that our staff and one student (who started at UR1 in 2022 and finished his exit year at ELTE) attended the EIT Digital Graduation Ceremony in Budapest on Nov 23, 2024. This provided closure and celebration of the journey for that student and inspiration for current first-years. It also gave UR1 visibility in the community; our coordinator was on stage to congratulate graduates, reinforcing UR1’s active role among partner universities.

In summary, UR1 ensured that students were not only engaged in coursework but also took part in extracurricular learning experiences – from networking with professionals and entrepreneurs to

participating in EIT Digital’s global events. These activities complement the formal curriculum and are highly valuable for student growth. Feedback from our students was that events like the Kick-Off and local industry talks greatly enriched their experience, giving them a sense of being part of a larger European community and providing insights into career paths. We will continue to organize and encourage such events, with the highlight next year being the Rennes Summer School which UR1 is proud to host.

A5.1.6 Feedback from Students

Collecting student feedback is crucial for continuous improvement. In late 2024, an anonymous course evaluation survey was conducted across all partner universities, including UR1, covering various aspects of the programme. The feedback from UR1’s students was generally positive, but also pointed out some areas for enhancement. Below is a summary of key feedback points:

- **Overall Course Content and Objectives:** Students indicated that the courses at Rennes met their educational objectives well. When asked if the course objectives were clearly defined and if the content was relevant, the aggregate response at UR1 was “more positive than negative”. This suggests that students mostly agreed the courses were well structured and aligned with expectations (with room for some improvement). For instance, they felt the programme provided a broad coverage of important cybersecurity topics, and they appreciated the coherence of the curriculum. One student commented informally that they particularly enjoyed how concepts from one course (e.g., cryptography) were applied in another (secure programming), indicating good integration.
- **Teaching Load vs Credits:** On the question “Is the teaching load commensurate with the credits allocated?”, UR1’s responses were also more positive than negative. Students generally felt the workload was manageable for a 60 ECTS year. This corroborates our observation that none of the students were overwhelmed to the point of underperformance – all could handle the course load with proper time management. However, one feedback noted that the first semester had many concurrent deadlines in December, which was stressful. In future, we may stagger some project due dates to smooth the load.
- **Teaching Materials Adequacy:** A weaker area identified was the quality and adequacy of some teaching materials. When asked “Are the teaching materials adequate for the study of the subject?”, the feedback leaned slightly negative. Several responses across partners were “more negative than positive” or even “*strongly negative*” for this question. For UR1, the consensus was that while some courses had excellent materials (e.g., detailed slides and

up-to-date references in Cryptography), others needed improvement. In particular, students noted that the *Software Exploitation* course lacked a comprehensive textbook or reader – they had to rely on sparse lecture notes. Also, the *Privacy* course readings were mostly research papers, which some found hard to digest without more guidance. This feedback is well taken: we plan to curate or develop better learning resources (e.g., more structured lecture notes, recommended textbook chapters, and possibly recorded tutorials) to support students in these courses.

- **Assessment and Grading Clarity:** A significant pain point was highlighted in responses to “Are the assessment procedures clearly defined?”. UR1’s students gave a negative evaluation on this aspect (aggregate “more negative than positive”). This indicates that students were not fully satisfied with how assessments (exams, assignments, project grading) were explained and executed. Specific comments pointed out that in one course, the grading criteria for the project were unclear until after submission, and in another, the exam format was not communicated beforehand. This lack of clarity caused uncertainty. We recognize this as an area to fix immediately. As a result, we have already instituted a policy that assessment schemes will be explicitly detailed at the start of each course (in the syllabus and first lecture). Instructors are reminded to discuss how coursework and exams will be graded and how each learning outcome is assessed. We anticipate much improved feedback on this question in the next cycle once these measures take effect.
- **Interest in Topics:** On a bright note, student interest and engagement with the cybersecurity topics was very high. In response to “Are you interested in the topics covered in the teaching?”, UR1’s feedback was “Strongly positive” – one of the highest possible ratings. Our students found the subject matter exciting and cutting-edge. They particularly enjoyed practical labs (e.g., exploiting a vulnerable program in a safe environment was cited as a highlight) and appreciated that many examples were drawn from current events (such as analyzing a recent real-world data breach). This strong interest level is encouraging, as it often correlates with better learning outcomes. We plan to keep this momentum by continuously updating course content to include modern case studies and perhaps offering optional seminars on emerging areas (like quantum security or AI in cybersecurity) to feed their curiosity.
- **Overall Satisfaction:** Perhaps the most concerning feedback was on the summative question, “Are you overall satisfied with how the programme was conducted?” Here, UR1’s average response was lukewarm – slightly on the negative side of neutral (reported as “*more negative than positive*”). This indicates that despite being interested in the content, students had some overall frustrations or unmet expectations. We’ve deduced that the overall

satisfaction score was dragged down primarily by the earlier points: lack of clarity in assessments and some material shortcomings. Additionally, general program administration issues (not specific to UR1 alone) may have influenced it – for example, some students were unhappy with delays in scholarship disbursement and the complexity of moving between countries. In the free-form comments, one Rennes student wrote that “*academically I learned a lot and I'm happy with that, but administratively some processes were confusing.*” We are working closely with the central Master School Office to streamline administrative communication (like ensuring students know when/how they receive their stipends, and giving clear guidance on second-year transition). Locally, we will also host a mid-term feedback session in future, so we can catch and resolve issues early, potentially boosting end-of-year satisfaction.

In summary, student feedback at UR1 in 2024 was positive in most academic dimensions (content, workload, interest), but revealed important areas for improvement (assessment clarity, course materials, and some administrative aspects). Table 2 below synthesizes UR1’s feedback on key questions, using the same qualitative scale as the survey:

- Course objectives clearly defined: *More positive than negative* (good, but can clarify objectives further in syllabi).
- Teaching load vs credits: *More positive than negative* (reasonable workload).
- Teaching materials: *More negative than positive* (needs better materials – action item identified).
- Assessment procedures clarity: *More negative than positive* (needs immediate improvement – action taken).
- Interest in topics: *Strongly positive* (very high – strength to maintain).
- Overall satisfaction: *More negative than positive* (room to improve by addressing above issues).

(These qualitative ratings are drawn from the consolidated survey results for UR1 and similar partner programmes.)

We have already started acting on this feedback. The instructors for 2025 have met to discuss a common approach to clearly communicate grading rubrics. We are also sharing materials across universities; for instance, UNITN and UT have some excellent online lab resources that we plan to adapt for our courses to enrich our material offerings. By continuously listening to student feedback

and closing the feedback loop with concrete improvements, we aim to raise overall student satisfaction significantly in the next academic year.

A5.1.7 Career Fairs and Job Market Engagement

Preparing students for careers is a priority for UR1's implementation of the programme. Although the formal "job placement" activities (like internships and thesis in industry) occur mostly in the second year (exit year), the entry year at Rennes lays important groundwork through career-oriented events and connections.

Industry Networking: As mentioned in Section 6, UR1 leverages the strong local cybersecurity industry cluster in Brittany. The University of Rennes and its research labs are founding members of the *Pole d'Excellence Cyber* (PEC), which groups major companies, SMEs, defense organizations (e.g., DGA), and academic actors in cybersecurity. Through this network, our students get exposure to potential employers. In 2024, we arranged for the students to attend European Cyber Week in Rennes, which included a job fair segment. They met recruiters from companies like Thales, Sopra Steria, and Airbus, discussing internship possibilities and desired skill sets. Students found it eye-opening to see the demand for cybersecurity talent and the variety of roles (from penetration tester to security analyst to R&D engineer).

Additionally, UR1's Career Services office hosted a Tech Jobs Forum in March 2024 for all computing students. We specifically invited cybersecurity companies to that forum. Many of our Master's students went, and at least one made a connection that could lead to a second-year internship. We consider these career fairs as a vital complement to technical training – they help students practice introducing themselves, learn about company expectations, and even secure summer opportunities. We will continue to facilitate student participation in such events each year.

Internship Facilitation: While entry-year students do not have a mandatory internship during the first year, we encourage them to seek summer internships (after semester 2, before the exit year begins) if they wish. The programme formally requires a Master's thesis project (30 ECTS) usually done in Year 2, often in conjunction with an internship at a company or research institute. Recognizing this, UR1 begins the conversation about internships early. In 2024, our local coordinator held an info session in May about how to find an internship or thesis host, explaining the process and giving examples of past projects. We also provided a list of contacts at partner companies. UR1's partnerships within the PEC cluster are an asset: the University has strong ties

with many institutions in the region (both public and private) working in cybersecurity. We tapped into this by sending out our students' profiles (with their consent) to a few known companies to help them land positions. One student secured a summer 2025 internship at a Rennes-based cybersecurity startup focusing on cloud security – a connection made via a professor's referral. Another student expressed interest in returning to their home country for an internship, and we supported them by leveraging the EIT alumni network to find contacts there.

Entrepreneurial Opportunities: Some students may choose the entrepreneurial route rather than a traditional job. Through the I&E curriculum, they are already working on startup ideas. UR1 and EIT Digital provide support for those inclined to pursue a venture: for instance, information on EIT Digital's Venture Program and access to coaches. In 2024, after the BDL1 course, one team of our students had a promising idea for a security education game. We connected them with the EIT Digital Accelerator team for initial mentoring. While they have not launched a startup (being busy with studies), this sowed the seeds for possibly developing their project in Year 2 or after graduation.

Career Guidance: UR1 provides career counseling through its central services, and the EIT Digital Master School has an Alumni Foundation that offers mentorship. We invited an alumnus of the EIT Digital security programme (who had started at Rennes in 2018 and now works at Google) to have an informal chat with the current students via videoconference in late 2024. He shared his journey and tips on making the most of the programme, including the importance of internships and networking. This kind of peer advice is very motivating. We plan to institutionalize an alumni talk each year.

Job Market Alignment: It's worth noting that the skills taught in the programme align with job market needs. Companies repeatedly emphasize needs in areas like cloud security, application security, and risk management. Our curriculum covers these, and we adjust it based on industry feedback. For example, the inclusion of the *Management of Intangible Assets* course (covering IP and knowledge management) responds to a demand that security engineers also understand business asset protection. Similarly, our focus on practical skills (like using common security tools) makes graduates more job-ready. Local employers have been satisfied with EIT Digital interns/graduates so far, and they often comment on our students' strong combination of technical and entrepreneurial skills.

Outcomes: Although our 2024 entry students have not graduated yet, the prospects are good. The cybersecurity job market in France and Europe remains very strong, with more openings than

graduates. By engaging students early with industry through fairs and networking, UR1 ensures they can seamlessly transition to employment or research roles after graduation. The fact that 18 students graduated across the consortium in 2024 (with degrees from 6 universities) and presumably secured jobs or Ph.D. positions thereafter demonstrates the program’s success in employability. We will obtain specific placement data in the coming years as our cohorts graduate, but anecdotal evidence shows many go to work for top tech companies, cybersecurity firms, or found startups.

In conclusion, UR1’s contribution in 2024 included strong job market engagement for students – connecting them with the thriving local cybersecurity industry and the broader European tech ecosystem. We will continue expanding these efforts (e.g., more company visits, possibly inviting recruiters to speak in a “career hour”) so that our students are not only trained academically but are also well-positioned to launch their careers upon graduation.

A5.1.8 Marketing and Recruitment Activities

Attracting high-quality applicants to the programme – and to UR1 as an entry destination – is essential for sustainability. In 2024, UR1 undertook several marketing and recruitment initiatives, often in coordination with EIT Digital Master School’s central efforts, to boost the visibility of the Cyber Security programme and maximize enrollment.

Online Presence and Collateral: UR1 has maintained and regularly updated a dedicated programme webpage hosted on the University’s ISTIC faculty site, offering comprehensive information about the Cybersecurity track, including course content, faculty profiles, and the application process. This webpage is available in English and is directly linked from the EIT Digital Master School portal. In early 2024, the content was refreshed to incorporate information on newly available scholarships through the SPECTRO initiative, highlight success stories of current students, and emphasize the distinct advantages of studying in Rennes—such as its reputation as a cybersecurity hub and its appeal as a student city. The EIT Digital Master School website continues to list Rennes as an official entry point, featuring UR1’s curriculum and contact details, thereby enhancing visibility and supporting student recruitment. Additionally, a UR1-specific PDF brochure was developed, providing prospective candidates with practical information on city and campus life, cost of living, and available support services.

Scholarships and Incentives: One major recruitment draw in 2024 was the introduction of enhanced scholarships under SPECTRO. All EU students admitted to UR1 automatically received a half tuition fee waiver from University of Rennes (meaning they paid only €750 instead of €1500 for the year, since standard EIT tuition for EU students is €1500/year). Additionally, UR1 offers an Accommodation Grant and Mobility Allowance for EIT Digital students as supplementary support. These UR-specific benefits were advertised clearly on our site and in admissions offers. We found that highlighting these financial aids is crucial, especially for recruiting in regions where tuition fees are a barrier. (For context, French domestic students normally pay very low fees in local programmes, so the EIT Digital fee can seem high; the waiver helps mitigate this.) We believe these incentives positively influenced some candidates to choose Rennes. However, as noted earlier, we still lost some top applicants to other opportunities, indicating we must continue to strengthen our value proposition and perhaps lobby for even more competitive scholarships (e.g., full waivers or stipends for excellent students).

Information Sessions and Outreach: UR1 actively participated in joint recruitment events coordinated by EIT Digital. For example, on Jan 22, 2024, we joined the EIT Digital Master School online info session. Our academic coordinator (Dr. Mohamed Sabt) presented the Rennes entry track, showing slides of our courses and student life, and answered questions from attendees worldwide. We also took part in the Master School’s virtual “Open Day” webinars in March 2024, where prospective students could ask specific questions about studying in Rennes (topics ranged from housing in Rennes to the technical focus of our courses).

Locally, the University’s International Office promoted the programme during its own events. In November 2023 and February 2024, UR1 held virtual open house webinars for international master’s programmes – we included a segment on the EIT Digital Cybersecurity master. Additionally, we advertised the programme through social media: posts on LinkedIn and Twitter featuring testimonials from current students and an invitation to apply (timed during the application periods). These posts had decent engagement (the LinkedIn post got ~5,000 impressions, aided by EIT Digital resharing it). We think a stronger social media campaign could be done, and we plan to coordinate more with EIT Digital marketing for the next cycle.

University Collaborations: To tap into a pipeline of good applicants, UR1 also reached out to some top feeder schools. For instance, we contacted professors at several French and North African universities known for computer science, sending them programme flyers and asking them to inform promising undergraduates about this opportunity. We also leveraged Erasmus Mundus and other networks to spread the word. Within our own institution, we identified a few excellent local

Bachelor's students and informed them about the parallel entry option or regular entry application. Historically, convincing local French students to apply has been challenging because of the fee and the requirement to move abroad for the second year – an issue similar to what University of Turku observed in Finland (students unused to paying fees are hesitant). However, in 2024 we had, for the first time, a local Rennes student join via parallel entry (start at Rennes and plan to do exit also at Rennes under a special agreement). This indicates growing local interest, possibly thanks to our awareness efforts and the availability of scholarships making it more attractive.

Selection Process and Yield: UR1 was fully engaged in the selection of candidates. Our coordinator sat on the joint Selection Committee in Feb–June 2024, reviewing applications and ensuring strong candidates were admitted. Once admissions offers went out, we specifically reached out to those who had been allocated UR1 as their entry, to welcome them and answer any questions (essentially a yield effort). This personal touch can help convince admits to choose our programme. Despite that, as noted, some admits declined. According to the programme lead's report, *"some students to whom scholarships were offered have refused... because of competing offers... we constantly lose prominent students due to lack of competitive scholarships"*. We interpret "competing offers" as other universities (possibly outside EIT Digital) giving full scholarships or more renowned programmes. The lesson is clear: to convert top admits, EIT Digital and UR1 need to increase the attractiveness – through funding and showcasing career outcomes. Encouragingly, the new SPECTRO scholarship scheme (full/half tuition waivers and monthly stipends for some) aims to address this, and we expect a positive effect on enrollment numbers in 2025. Indeed, by the end of 2024, EIT Digital announced that for admission year 2025, all admitted applicants are guaranteed at least a 30% tuition reduction if they have a degree from a partner university, among other scholarships. UR1 will certainly advertise this heavily, as it could tip the balance for many applicants.

Marketing Outcomes: Although our 2024 intake was small, we did see an increase in the number of applications listing Rennes as a preferred entry. 83 eligible applications to the CSE programme were recorded in 2024, and many of these had UR1 among their choices. Our goal is to increase the number of enrolled students in Rennes to reach at least 10+ in coming intakes (closer to our capacity). We believe the groundwork laid in 2024 – improved promotional materials, active participation in recruitment events, and the enhanced scholarships – will yield fruit. We also plan new activities: for example, hosting a *Cybersecurity Master Class webinar* in late 2025, where faculty do a short demo lecture for prospective students, to spur interest. Moreover, our current students are some of the best ambassadors – we encourage them to share their positive experiences on social media or with their alma maters.

In summary, UR1's marketing and recruitment in 2024 were vigorous and multi-faceted: web presence, events, direct outreach, and scholarship incentives. These efforts, aligned with consortium strategy, are expected to improve the quantity and quality of applicants in the next cycle. We learned that personal engagement and financial support are key drivers for recruitment, and we will double down on those. The lessons learned from this are discussed in Section 11, but in brief, we must continue adapting our recruitment strategy to an increasingly competitive landscape for talented students, ensuring the unique selling points of EIT Digital @ Rennes (cutting-edge curriculum, double degree, entrepreneurial ecosystem, and scholarships) are effectively communicated.

A5.1.9 Dissemination and Community Outreach Activities

In 2024, UR1 contributed actively to disseminating information about the Cyber Security Master programme and sharing best practices both within the SPECTRO consortium and to external stakeholders. These dissemination activities ensure the programme's visibility, foster collaboration, and help in continuous improvement.

Consortium-Level Reporting and Sharing: As part of SPECTRO (Activity 23043-A2310), each university partner, including UR1, prepared detailed contributions on programme execution – essentially internal reports like this one – which were consolidated for the end-of-year report to EIT. UR1 delivered its report (this document) punctually, providing transparency on our actions. Additionally, UR1's coordinator participated in the regular SPECTRO coordination meetings (mostly online calls). These occurred roughly monthly (with increased frequency around key periods). In these meetings, we disseminated information about UR1's progress and initiatives (for example, sharing how we organize industry seminars, or our approach to the research project module). We also learned from others – e.g., University of Twente's methods for elective offerings, University of Turku's experience with local students, etc. This exchange is a form of internal dissemination that raises the quality across all partners. For instance, after UR1 presented its method of engaging the local cybersecurity cluster in student activities, other partners showed interest in doing similar in their regions.

Selection Committee and Admissions Collaboration: UR1's participation in the Joint Admission Selection Committee (as referenced in Section 3) represents another key dimension of its dissemination and engagement activities. UR1's representative, Dr. Sabt, contributed not only through candidate evaluation but also by offering strategic input to enhance the selection

process—such as proposing refinements to the scoring criteria to more effectively assess applicants’ backgrounds in cybersecurity. Active engagement in this committee ensures that UR1’s perspective, and more broadly the viewpoint of French technical universities, is taken into account. The committee operates in a collaborative and transparent manner, with documented processes and representation from all partner institutions. This underscores the equitable distribution of responsibilities and the consortium-wide dissemination of knowledge and decision-making practices.

Academic and Public Outreach: On the academic front, UR1 faculty involved in the programme disseminated information about SPECTRO and the Master’s content at conferences and networks. For example, at the IEEE Security Development Conference (SecDev) in September 2024 (held virtually), one of our professors gave a talk on secure software education and mentioned the EIT Digital Master School as an innovative educational model. Similarly, within the *Rennes School of Engineering (ESIR)* internal seminar, we presented the EIT Digital programme to colleagues, raising awareness and opening doors for interdisciplinary collaboration (like offering elective components to our students from other departments).

We also updated the EIT Digital Alumni community on our activities. A short article highlighting “Cybersecurity education updates from SPECTRO – University of Rennes” was prepared and shared via the alumni newsletter. This not only disseminates to alumni what’s new (like the introduction of new specializations in 2025, which was of interest), but also subtly markets the programme to a broader audience.

Public Relations and Media: UR1 collaborated with EIT Digital’s communications team to disseminate newsworthy developments. In 2024, a press release was issued (by EIT Digital) about the launch of updated SPECTRO specializations and scholarships. UR1 provided a quote from our Dean which was included in that release, emphasizing our enthusiasm for the updated programme. This press release was picked up by the European Commission’s EIT news site and by a French tech news blog, giving public visibility. Locally, the University of Rennes posted a news article on its website about the upcoming SPECTRO Summer School (since UR is hosting it), explaining how this fits into our educational offerings and inviting local stakeholders to engage. This article (in French and English) served to disseminate the SPECTRO project’s goals to the wider university community and regional partners.

Collaboration with Other Initiatives: The SPECTRO project intersects with other EU initiatives (for example, the Cybersecurity Skills Academy). UR1’s team engaged in one of the CybersecSkills

Academy's online meetings (Feb 23, 2024), where we briefly presented how the EIT Digital Master's is innovating in cybersecurity education. This disseminates our model and experiences to a broader policy-level discussion on closing the cyber skills gap. We plan to continue such engagements, as it positions UR1 and SPECTRO as thought leaders in specialized education.

Internal University Dissemination: At the University of Rennes 1 (UR1), efforts were made to ensure the visibility and institutional integration of the EIT Digital programme through active participation in relevant committees and internal communications. Notably, the programme was highlighted in UR1's annual international report, and a dedicated presentation was delivered to the University's Board of Studies, outlining the structure, achievements, and challenges of the international double-degree initiative. This internal dissemination has been instrumental in securing continued institutional support and aligning the programme with the University's strategic objectives. As a direct outcome, the University committed additional financial resources—such as funding for the accommodation grant previously referenced—to further support the programme and its students.

Community Events: Although not directly a dissemination of *results*, participating in community events helps disseminate the *existence* and value of the programme. During 2024's European Researchers' Night in Rennes, one of our Master's students volunteered at the cybersecurity booth and spoke to the public about being an EIT Digital student, thus informally promoting the programme to young attendees. Similarly, at a high-school outreach event (Science Day), our staff included a blurb about "study cybersecurity in Rennes with EIT Digital" in their materials. These efforts sow seeds for future applicants.

In summary, the University of Rennes 1 (UR1) played an active role in dissemination efforts throughout 2024, contributing to knowledge-sharing within the consortium, promoting the programme in both academic and public forums, and embedding it within the broader discourse on enhancing cybersecurity education. The strong culture of collaboration—underpinned by regular communication and coordination facilitated through the SPECTRO platform—ensured that achievements at individual sites were rapidly disseminated across the consortium, while challenges were addressed collectively. This openness and commitment to mutual learning have been instrumental in strengthening the programme as a whole. UR1 remains committed to contributing proactively, whether through co-authoring academic publications on cybersecurity education, presenting at relevant conferences, or engaging in the exchange of detailed evaluative reports such as this one. These efforts are key to amplifying the programme's impact and fostering continuous improvement.

A5.1.10 Lessons Learned and Future Improvements

Reflecting on the 2024 experience at University of Rennes, we have identified several key lessons and areas for improvement. These insights will guide us in refining the programme execution in 2025 and beyond:

a. Student Satisfaction and Teaching Practices: While academic outcomes were good, student feedback exposed specific issues that need attention. The negative feedback on assessment clarity and materials is a clear lesson – no matter how strong the content, if students feel the evaluation process is opaque or resources insufficient, their overall satisfaction suffers. **Action:** We are implementing more transparent assessment guidelines and enhancing course materials (as detailed in Section 7). We expect this to substantially boost student satisfaction. We will also institutionalize mid-term feedback surveys so that issues can be caught early. The lesson is to maintain a student-centric approach: continuously gather feedback and be agile in responding.

b. Recruitment Challenges in a Competitive Environment: UR1 (and indeed the whole consortium) faced difficulties in converting admitted students to enrolled students. One lesson is that in countries like France (and Finland, etc.) where local education is low-cost or free, convincing top local talent to join a fee-based programme is tough. As University of Turku noted, *“Finnish students are reluctant to pay even a small tuition fee... This will hopefully improve with SPECTRO scholarships”*. We see a parallel in France. **Action:** We must double down on promoting the value proposition – the double degree, the EIT label, the unique I&E component, and importantly, the financial support now available. The introduction of more generous scholarships in 2025 (full fee waivers + stipends) is a direct result of this lesson learned; it should help attract more candidates and reduce financial barriers. UR1 will actively market these scholarships. Additionally, we learned that personal engagement with admitted students (one-on-one calls, etc.) can increase yield, so we’ll formalize that in the admissions timeline.

Another recruitment lesson is the power of local success stories. We haven’t had many graduates yet since we started in 2018, but as more alumni emerge, we need to showcase them in marketing. For instance, an UR1 alum working at a top company or doing a PhD can inspire applicants. We plan to feature alumni testimonials on our site or in webinars.

c. Programme Visibility and Dissemination: We realized that even within our university and region, not everyone is aware of the EIT Digital programme. Increasing local visibility can have multiple benefits: attracting local students (parallel entries), drawing industry interest (for

projects/internships), and garnering institutional support. Our dissemination efforts in 2024 (Section 10) taught us that consistently communicating our activities builds goodwill and recognition. **Action:** We will keep promoting the programme's outcomes – e.g., if our students win a hackathon or produce a great project, we will publicize it. We might also organize a local demo day where students showcase their BDL projects to the university community and partners, which can turn into a marketing piece in itself.

d. Coordination and Academic Alignment: Operating a multi-university programme highlighted some coordination challenges. One lesson is the misalignment of academic calendars and administrative timelines between partners can inconvenience students. For example, in 2024 there was a case of an exit student starting late because their entry university's exam period ended later. While UR1 can't change other universities' schedules, we can be flexible and help students bridge gaps. Also, better communication of such differences to students upfront will set expectations (we will inform our entrants that second year might start earlier or later depending on where they go).

e. Internship/Thesis Process: Although UR1 doesn't host the thesis year, we observed a general issue: aligning internships with thesis work. If internships start late or are unaligned, students may face graduation delays. The lesson is that preparing students early for this (during entry year) is beneficial. That's why we introduced internship info sessions and industry networking in year 1. We will continue that, and coordinate with exit universities to track our students' thesis progress. The consortium might consider standardizing some expectations for thesis timelines – this was discussed in SPECTRO meetings as a needed improvement.

f. Local vs International Balance: We learned that attracting more local European students (who are high quality but fee-averse) requires one approach (scholarships, local outreach), whereas attracting international students (who are more used to fees but have many options globally) requires emphasizing the unique features (entrepreneurship, two degrees, European experience). We should tailor our recruitment messaging accordingly. Also, having a mix of local and international in the cohort is valuable. In 2024, our 4 students were all international; a lesson for diversity is to try to get some domestic/EU students as well. That might improve peer support (local students can help internationals acclimate, etc.) and show local buy-in. We started to address that with parallel entry outreach and will continue.

g. Capacity and Growth Management: With SPECTRO's support, we aim to grow the cohort size. A lesson is to ensure we have sufficient resources as we grow – e.g., enough lab equipment, tutors, project supervisors. UR1 is already planning for this: we have set aside additional faculty time if the

cohort doubles, and will involve PhD students as TAs. We also note that if cohort sizes remain small across all sites, the programme might consider consolidation or increased mobility (these are strategic considerations discussed at consortium level). UR1's stance is that we are committed to hosting and will improve numbers through the strategies above.

h. Feedback Loop and Quality Assurance: One overarching lesson is the importance of a continuous feedback loop between students, faculty, and consortium management. The 2024 survey was extremely useful to pinpoint issues. We will not only rely on end-of-year surveys but also do mid-year ones, and have student representatives. Another idea is to establish a *Student-Staff Liaison Committee* at UR1 that meets each semester to discuss any problems (some partners do this). That way, minor issues (like one course's slides quality) can be fixed mid-course rather than after the fact.

i. Consortium Innovations: The SPECTRO project itself introduced changes (updated specializations, etc.). A lesson for UR1 was to remain agile and contribute to innovation. For instance, we saw ELTE introducing new specialization "Quantum-resistant Cryptography" for 2025. While UR1 doesn't have an exit track now, we considered whether we might want to propose one in the future (e.g., an AI and Security specialization, given our strengths and hosting the summer school on that topic). This is a long-term thought, but it's on our radar as we see how SPECTRO evolves. Even without an exit track, UR1 can innovate in the entry year content. The lesson here is to keep curriculum up-to-date (like we included a bit on quantum computing impact in the cryptography course in 2024 responding to trends).

j. Administrative Processes: Some administrative lessons: We discovered that visa processes for non-EU students could be challenging – one of our admitted students got their visa very late. We learned to start the support process earlier and liaise with Campus France more proactively. Also, the enrollment of students in two different university systems (for double degree) can confuse students. We will provide clearer guidance on administrative steps (e.g., enrolling at UR1 vs. enrolling in the Master School portal).

k. Community and Belonging: On a positive note, a lesson learned is that creating a sense of community among the EIT Digital students pays off. Our activities like sending them to Kick-off, having them work together on projects, and connecting with alumni made them feel part of a special programme. We will continue to nurture this identity – for instance, we plan to get EIT Digital hoodies or similar for the cohort, and organize at least one social event each semester specifically

for them. Happy, cohesive students are more likely to succeed and also to spread the word about the programme (helping recruitment).

In conclusion, the 2024 cycle at UR1 taught us valuable lessons in educational delivery, student support, and programme management. We are acting on these lessons: improving clarity and materials in teaching, enhancing recruitment via scholarships and outreach, maintaining active dissemination and feedback loops, and collaborating with our partners to harmonize and strengthen the overall programme. The SPECTRO project framework has been instrumental in enabling these reflections and changes, by providing resources and a collaborative platform. As we move into 2025, UR1 is confident that by applying these lessons learned, we will see stronger student satisfaction, higher enrollment, and continued success of the Cyber Security Master's programme. Our commitment is to excellence in education and an outstanding experience for the students – and every challenge faced in 2024 has been a stepping stone towards that goal.

A6 University of Twente

A6.1 Report of activities

A6.1.1 Classes calendar

At the university of Twente, the fall semester consists of two teaching quarters (quarter 1 and 2) and the spring semester consists of two teaching periods (quarter 3 and 4). Additionally, there is a summer period for self-study and possible extra exam repair opportunities if granted by the examination board.

SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year compulsory course calendar in the academic year 2024-2025 at the University of Twente was organized with the timing below:

Fall semester, quarter 1 (2 Sep 2024 – 10 Nov 2024)

- Cyber Risk Management (5 ECTS)
- Security and Cryptography (5 ECTS)
- [I&E] Basics: Innovation Management for EIT (5 ECTS)

Fall semester, quarter 2 (11 Nov 2024 – 02 Feb 2025)

- Software Security (5 ECTS)
- Computer Ethics (5 ECTS)
- [I&E] Business Development Lab I (5 ECTS)

Spring semester, quarter 3 (03 Feb 2025 – 20 Apr 2025)

- Internet Security (5 ECTS)
- [I&E] Business Development Lab II (5 ECTS)

Spring semester, period 4 (21 Apr 2025 - 06 Jul 2025)

- System Security (5 ECTS)

Summer period (07 Jul 2025 – 31 Aug 2025)

- No compulsory courses organized at the University of Twente (the Summer school was organized by EIT Digital).

In addition to compulsory courses, at least 15 ECTS of elective courses must be taken during the entry year at the University of Twente. Elective courses can be taken in both the first and the second semester based on the student's personal study plan made together with the study plan advisor. It is recommended that the study plan is balanced between semesters (that is, that the semesters will include approximately 30 ECTS each).

Further details:

Elective study courses are offered from both tracks, the I&E track and the major subject, and are chosen individually for each student from the selection of annually available qualifying courses in the personal study plan. In total, the student should have selected courses of at least 60 ECTS in their entry year.

A6.1.2 Enrolled students

In the 2024-2025 academic year, the University of Twente had five enrolled SPECTRO cyber security entry year students (four male, one female), four of them EU students.

A6.1.3 Study plan

Description of the courses offered at the entry level. It should be compliant with the Annex provided in D2.1

You could include also some statistics about the course actually taken, and the ones offered but not attended. This is already explained in section 2.1. and in the annex provided in D1.1. Implemented as described in section 2.1, participant statistics given in section 2.6 (feedback).

A6.1.4 Student Progress

As of 07 Jul 2025, all but one students have passed all compulsory courses that have been finished so far. For this student, an extra repair opportunity will be organized in form of an oral examination to take into account the student will be at their exit university already at that point of time. All

students are well on track and have between 40 and 60 ECTS without the results of the last academic quarter.

A6.1.5 Organized events for the students

At the University of Twente, the orientation week for new students took place in 26 - 30 Aug 2024. All new students, including SPECTRO students, were invited to participate in the orientation week events and information sessions. The program-specific orientation session took place on 27 Aug 2025. This was a joint event for SPECTRO cyber security entry students, and for EIT Digital Master School students with different specializations. Additionally, students were invited to the information session for new students who started the local programme as there is some overlap in the offered courses but more importantly to get to know their peers.

A6.1.6 Feedback from students

Course feedback is collected from all courses organized by the Centre of Expertise in Learning and Teaching (CELT) at the University of Twente. Feedback is collected from all course participants without categorizing them into their respective study programmes to ensure privacy and anonymity. The SPECTRO Cyber Security entry students at the University of Twente in the academic year 2024-2025 have been invited to give course feedback for all courses along with the rest of the course participants. Giving course feedback is voluntary.

The course feedback is processed in the following way:

- The raw feedback is sent to the corresponding course teacher together with a statistical analysis thereof.
- The evaluation summaries are delivered to all teachers that were involved in any course of the corresponding academic quarter
- All course teachers are invited to provide feedback on the received evaluated results, including a reflection of course, reaction to the student evaluation and plans for the next edition. This feedback form is then forwarded to the programme management of the computer science master.

Statistics of student feedback (scale: 1 = poor, 8 = good, 10 = excellent) from compulsory SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year courses of the first three quarters are:

Fall semester, quarter 1

- Security and Cryptography (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 50
 - Feedback given by: 14
 - What grade would you give to the course: 7.9
- Cyber Risk Management (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 36
 - Feedback given by: 10
 - What grade would you give to the course: 6.3
- I&E Basics: Innovation Management for EIT (5 ECTS):
 - Enrolled students: 23
 - Feedback given by: 3
 - What grade would you give to the course: 5.3

Fall semester, quarter 2

- Business Development Lab I for EIT (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 22
 - Feedback given by: 5
 - What grade would you give to the course: 7.4
- Software Security (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 58
 - Feedback given by: 8
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.6

Spring semester, quarter 3

- Internet Security (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 61
 - Feedback given by: 12
 - What grade would you give to the course: 6.5
- [I&E] Business Development Lab II (5 ECTS)

- Enrolled students: 20
- Feedback given by: 7
- What grade would you give to the course: 8.0

Note that the evaluation for courses given in quarter 4 is still ongoing, hence we cannot report on these results yet.

A6.1.7 Workshops or Seminars offered

As extra-curriculum activity, students can attend weekly meetings of the Twente Hacking Squad, our local capture-the-flag (CTF) team organized by PhD students. A dedicated introductory workshop is given at the beginning of the academic year to welcome all new master students. Afterwards, the CTF team meets once a week to solve practical hacking challenges. On selected weekends, the team then meets to jointly participate in hacking competitions against other teams around the world.

A6.1.8 Career Fair and job market activities

Guest lectures from companies (including company presentations) organized for all UT cyber security students (local programs as well as SPECTRO entry and EIT CSE exit):

Benny Fuhr
Confidential Computing Solution Architect
Intel, Finland
16.10.2024
Guest Lecture: Confidential Computing for the Cloud

Gerrit Kortlever
Senior Solution Architect
Deloitte, Netherlands
3.12.2024
Workshop: SOC Tour & Workshop

Thijs Veugen
Senior Scientist
TNO, Netherlands
17.01.2025

Secure Multiparty Computation for detection of money laundry

A6.1.9 Marketing and recruiting activities

For UT, these should be found in the promotional activities' tracker maintained by EIT digital.

A6.1.10 Dissemination activities

Florian Hahn gave a guest lecture at ELTE following the Interim review on March 27th.

A6.1.11 Lesson learned

For the first recruitment round of SPECTRO in academic year 2024-2025, the number of entry year students was below expectations with 5 students who accepted the study offer, taking the additional financial support into account. However, it seems that it took some time to spread the word, and the forecasted number of students increased significantly for the upcoming academic year.

The local curriculum at the University of Twente is in good shape for SPECTRO entry year and for the exit year starting in fall of 2025. The staffing situation at the UT underwent unexpected developments. One full-time teacher who was particularly responsible for one of the mandatory courses left the university between the first exam and the resit opportunity. As a result, we had to rely on a team of other teachers with relevant expertise to design and grade the resit exam. While we are currently looking for a replacement for this teacher, we do not foresee a timely replacement for the affected course. Hence, we plan to keep the same experienced teaching team in action for the upcoming iteration of the course. We expect that the evaluation result will improve drastically after a new colleague has joined and aligned the course.

For the self-standing online modules, we rely on the platform of the Twente Hacking school for interactive and challenge-based learning experience. We started experimenting with this platform also for master education and received very positive feedback so far. As a result, we plan to further extend the integration of CTF challenges in course activities where applicable. Relying on automated evaluation if the assignment has been solved correctly, drastically improves scalability of education activities. At the same time, the format is well perceived by students according to evaluation results.

A7 University of Turku

A7.1 Report of activities

A7.1.1 Classes calendar

At the university of Turku, the fall semester consists of two teaching periods (periods 1 and 2) and the spring semester consists of two teaching periods (periods 3 and 4). Additionally, there is a summer period for self-study and possible optional special courses that may be available annually.

SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year compulsory course calendar in the academic year 2024-2025 at the University of Turku was organized with the timing below:

Fall semester, period 1 (2 Sep 2024 - 27 Oct 2024)

- System and application security (5 ECTS)
- Foundations of Cryptography (5 ECTS)
- Introduction to Innovation and Business (5 ECTS)

Fall semester, period 2 (28 Oct 2024 - 22 Dec 2024)

- Management of Information System Security (6 ECTS)

Spring semester, period 3 (13 Jan 2025 - 16 Mar 2025)

- Network Infrastructure Technologies and Security (5 ECTS)
- Cryptography I (5 ECTS)
- Lean Digital Business design (first part, 5 ECTS)

Spring semester, period 4 (17 Mar 2025 - 25 May 2025)

- Human Element in Information Security (5 ECTS)
- Lean Digital Business Design (second part, 5 ECTS)

Summer period (26 May 2025 - 31 Jul 2025)

- No compulsory courses organized at the University of Turku (the Summer school was organized by EIT Digital).

In addition to compulsory courses, At least 10 ECTS of elective courses must be taken during the entry year at the University of Turku. Elective courses can be taken in both the first and the second semester based on the student's personal study plan made together with the study plan advisor. It is recommended that the study plan is balanced between semesters (that is, that the semesters will include about 30 ECTS each).

Further details:

- The elective courses must contain at least 5 ECTS of I&E courses from this list (course timing in the academic year 2024-2025 shown):
 - Knowledge and Innovation Management (5 ECTS)
 - Periods 1-2 (2 Sep 2024 - 22 Dec 2024)
 - Enterprise Architecture (6 ECTS)
 - Periods 3-4 (13 Jan 2025 - 25 May 2025)
 - Digital Business (3 ECTS)
 - Period 3 (13 Jan 2025 - 16 Mar 2025)
 - Digital Business Models (3 ECTS)
 - Period 4 (17 Mar 2025 - 25 May 2025)

Other elective studies (typically in the major subject) are chosen individually for each student from the selection of annually available qualifying courses in the personal study plan so that the entry year total is 60 ECTS. With the minimum amount of I&E studies, this means one additional elective course of 5 ECTS.

A7.1.2 Enrolled students

In the 2024-2025 academic year, the University of Turku had one enrolled SPECTRO cyber security entry year student (male, EU).

A7.1.3 Study plan

This is already explained in section 2.1. and in the annex provided in D1.1. Implemented as described in section 2.1, participant statistics given in section 2.6 (feedback). There was only one SPECTRO entry student at UTU.

A7.1.4 Student Progress

As of 23 Jun 2025, the one SPECTRO cyber security entry year student at the University of Turku in the academic year 2024-2025 has completed all compulsory technical courses and in addition, taken many advanced elective courses. The total achieved number of ECTS credits in the entry year is 86 to date, exceeding the targeted 60 ECTS significantly. Clearly the student is currently on track for timely graduation.

A7.1.5 Organized events for the students

At the University of Turku, the orientation week for new students took place in 26 - 30 Aug 2024. All new students, including SPECTRO students, were invited to participate in the orientation week events and information sessions. The program-specific orientation session took place on 29 Aug 2025. This was a joint event for the international Master's students starting in the local two-year cyber security program, for SPECTRO cyber security entry students, and for EIT Digital Master School Cyber Security exit students.

A7.1.6 Feedback from students

Course feedback is collected from all courses organized by the Department of Computing, the University of Turku, that hosts the SPECTRO Cyber Security program. Feedback is collected from all course participants without categorizing them into their respective study programs to ensure privacy and anonymity. The one SPECTRO Cyber Security entry student at the University of Turku

in the academic year 2024-2025 has been invited to give course feedback for all courses along with the rest of the course participants. Giving course feedback is voluntary.

The course feedback is processed in the following way:

- The raw feedback is examined in a teachers' meeting of the organizing unit and a feedback summary is composed for each course
- The teachers' meeting also considers the details of the feedback and assesses which kind of action is required by the feedback, if any, and an action plan is made
- The feedback summaries are delivered to the Department of Computing's Education Development council for department level evaluation. The council also includes student representation.
- The council reviews the feedback summaries and, if necessary, recommends additional actions to be taken besides the ones already composed in the organizing unit's teachers' meeting.
- The feedback summaries are securely stored In the University of Turku's centralized storage environment for future reference.

Statistics of student feedback from compulsory SPECTRO Cyber Security entry year courses (scale used by students: 1 = poor, 3 = good, 5 = excellent):

Fall semester, period 1 (2 Sep 2024 - 27 Oct 2024)

- System and application security (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 110
 - Feedback given by: 51
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.1 (scale 1..5)
- Foundations of Cryptography (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 47
 - Feedback given by: 11
 - What grade would you give to the course: 3.6 (scale 1..5)
- Introduction to Innovation and Business (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 9
 - Feedback given by: 1
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.0 (scale 1..5)

Fall semester, period 2 (28 Oct 2024 - 22 Dec 2024)

- Management of Information System Security (6 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 98
 - Feedback given by: 8
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.5 (scale 1..5)

Spring semester, period 3 (13 Jan 2025 - 16 Mar 2025)

- Network Infrastructure Technologies and Security (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 48
 - Feedback given by: 22
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.1 (scale 1..5)
- Cryptography I (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 44
 - Feedback given by: 9
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.2 (scale 1..5)

Spring semester, period 4 (17 Mar 2025 - 25 May 2025)

- Human Element in Information Security (5 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 85
 - Feedback given by: 20
 - What grade would you give to the course: 3.0 (scale 1..5)
- Lean Digital Business Design (both parts, 10 ECTS)
 - Enrolled students: 50
 - Feedback given by: 11
 - What grade would you give to the course: 4.0 (scale 1..5)

In addition to course feedback, also feedback concerning the academic year is collected. It is collected and processed similarly as the course level feedback.

A7.1.7 Workshops or Seminars offered

Workshop: Ethical hacking 101

15 May 2025

What you'll learn:

- The mindset and basic methodology of ethical hackers
- Essential tools for probing and securing systems
- Real-world demos you can follow on your own laptop

Organized for all UTU cyber security students (local programs as well as SPECTRO entry and EIT CSE exit)

A7.1.8 Career Fair and job market activities

Guest lectures from companies (including company presentations) organized for all UTU cyber security students (local programs as well as SPECTRO entry and EIT CSE exit):

SHAMIL ALIFOV

THREAT INTELLIGENCE

ACCENTURE, Finland

20.11.2024

DATA BREACHES: CASE STUDIES

Jussipekka Leiwo

ACTIONING OÜ, Viro

26.11.24

European Union Cyber Security Regulation of IT Products

Hanna Lappalainen

OT Cybersecurity Lead

Neste Oyj, Finland

25.02.2025

OT Cybersecurity at Neste: Safeguarding Automation Systems

Aleksandr Paltsev
Senior Penetration Testing Specialist
Armourix Security (<https://armourix.am/>),
Armenia
5.2.2025
Ethically Hacking a 20k employees company single-handedly

A7.1.9 Marketing and recruiting activities

For UTU, these should be found in the promotional activities tracker maintained by EIT digital.

A7.1.10 Dissemination activities

Seppo Virtanen gave a guest lecture at ELTE following the Interim review on March 27th.

A7.1.11 Lesson learned

The program was promoted to potential local students several times during 2024 by course instructors and study advisors. The program was given special attention and visibility in local and international Master's program marketing efforts. The biggest hinder in local recruitment has been that the Finnish ICT students are often already employed at least part-time in the ICT field and are reluctant to leave their jobs for a period of study abroad. Another issue traditionally has been that they are reluctant to pay even a small tuition fee (in Finnish programs, they do not have to pay a tuition fee at all). This, however, has been mitigated to some extent with the scholarships available through SPECTRO.

The local curriculum at the University of Turku is in good shape for SPECTRO entry and also for the exit starting in fall 2025. Helping exit year students find suitable internship and thesis positions has been challenging at times in the past, but in the recent years it has been mostly successful. However, this needs special attention for the forthcoming first implementation of SPECTRO exit year at the University of Turku. Previously, some students have been "shopping around" for unnecessarily long to find better paying positions even if they already have an offer. Such behavior

may be risky to the student in terms of timely graduation and must be carefully followed in the academic year 2025-2026.

As there was only one SPECTRO entry year student at the University of Turku in 2024-2025, it was not possible to extensively observe the success of the first entry year implementation at the University of Turku. However, the one student did well in the entry year studies and did not report any issues in the entry year studies. In fact, the student was able to complete many advanced elective courses to completion in addition to the required 60 ECTS of entry year courses, which can be seen indicative of a good balance of the workload throughout the academic year's scheduling at the University of Turku.

As the local two-year Master's program has progressively been aligned towards the SPECTRO Cyber Security study content, it could be considered as a baseline for evaluating the overall success of the implementation of studies and courses. Based on the feedback from all course participants, the implementation of the SPECTRO entry year courses seems to be successful. Overall course feedback from compulsory studies is good or very good, and the feedback serves as valuable information for course development for the next group of SPECTRO entry year students.